

Roadmap for replicability of new plastic packaging value chain across EU

CIRC-PACK - Towards circular economy in
the plastic packaging value chain

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ABBREVIATIONS

CIRC-PACK	Towards circular economy in the plastic packaging value chain
CEIS	Circular Economy Indicator System
DC	Demo Case
EoL	End-Of-Life
GWP	Global Warming Potential
LCA:	Life Cycle Assessment
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
WP	Work Package

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7/ Tecnopackaging	TECNO
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13/ Asociación Española de Normalización y Certificación	AENOR
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22/ PLASTIPOLIS	PLASTIPOLIS

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The aim of this deliverable is the identification of a roadmap for replicability of new plastic packaging value chains. Indeed, the replication of a business model and of a value chain in general is crucial to ensure a visible and tangible impact of the activities performed within the project at higher scale and the preliminary identification of interesting geographical locations in which a potential of success is foreseen.

To this purpose, the first chapter analyses the **country-specific aspects that can facilitate replicability in the plastic packaging value chain**, also based on the results obtained by the Circular Economy Indicator System (CEIS) application.

As a preliminary high-level assessment, a selection of **material indicators, R&D indicators, economic indicators and social indicators** – considered as proxies of the degree of implementation of circular economy applications in each European country is identified and reported, namely: recycling rate of plastic packaging, circular material use rate, number of patents related to recycling and secondary raw materials, value added at factor cost, gross investment in tangible goods, person employed (for the recycling sector, repair and reuse sector and rental and leasing sector, with reference to the last three indicators). Thus, based on the performance of each country with respect to these indicators, Germany, The Netherlands, Spain, Italy and United Kingdom are identified **as countries presenting a positive or very positive performance in terms of status of advancement of circular economy**, implying a good potential for the replicability of CIRCPACK innovations.

A quantitative assessment is also performed, based on data available from ongoing work in D2.4. In detail, the **sensitivity of the results of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) to the variation of selected national-based parameters** is studied. In this context, the identified national-based factors are the **electricity mix** and the **end-of-life** route. It is observed that the highest achievable benefits from varying the electricity mix are in terms of global warming potential and terrestrial acidification. On the other hand, benefits from varying the EoL scenario range up to over 200% in terms of global warming potential, but significant benefits are also calculated for fossil resource scarcity for some value chains. Moreover, the **sensitivity of the OPEX costs to the variation of the costs of electricity supply** is analysed.

In addition, the **distance thresholds to ensure sustainability** of the innovative value chains with respect to traditional practice are estimated for different means of transportation, whenever applicable, based on the global warming potential indicator.

Subsequently, the second chapter introduces and validates a selection **of technical and non-technical replicability requirements**, which should be fulfilled by a city/a region/a country to facilitate a smooth development and exploitation of circular value chains.

The technical requirements are:

- availability and relevance of local resources;
- waste collection and separation capacity;
- waste reprocessing capacity;
- functional clusterization of industries on territory;

whereas the non-technical requirements are:

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- existence of a market demand;
- support of governments to improve circular value chains: policy framework, financing and administrative burden;
- engagement of enterprises in promoting circular economy;
- customers' awareness about circular economy and environmental.

Based on the results of a survey carried out among the CIRCPACK partners, it emerged that waste collection and separation capacity, waste reprocessing capacity and the enforcement of a consistent national policy framework are the most important driver for the implementation of circular economy value chains, and they should be considered with high priority.

Finally, based on the aforementioned replicability requirements, **6 cities potentially suitable for the replication of circular value chains in the plastic packaging sector**, based on CIRCPACK demo cases are presented. Such cities are identified through a set of interviews, dedicated to representative members of the municipality, and they are: Turin, Zagreb, Freiburg, Sevilla, Kartal and Porto.

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INTRODUCTION

The present deliverable D6.5 “Roadmap for replicability of new plastic packaging value chain across EU” is the core outcome of Task 6.4 “Roadmap for replicability of new plastic packaging value chain across EU”, within the context of WP6 “Cross sectoral validation, replicability and upscaling of solutions”.

The aim of this document is, as indicated by the title, the identification of a roadmap for replicability of new plastic packaging value chains. Indeed, the replication of a business model and of a value chain in general is crucial to ensure a visible and tangible impact of the activities performed within the project at higher scale and the preliminary identification of interesting geographical locations in which a potential of success is foreseen.

Considering the variety of factors and approaches that can be used to study such aspect, the document is structured into three core chapters, each addressing the theme of replicability from different perspective.

In details, the first chapter analyses the country-specific aspects that can facilitate replicability in the plastic packaging value chain, also based on the results obtained by the CEIS application. In addition, it focuses on the distance thresholds to ensure sustainability.

The second chapter introduces and validates a selection of technical and non-technical replicability requirements, which should be fulfilled by a city/a region/a country to facilitate a smooth development and exploitation of circular value chains.

Finally, the third chapter aims at identifying potential real cases for replication in the project’s represented countries, through a set of interviews to cities’ representatives.

As a general approach, the work developed is an intersection of desk activities, external inputs and internal inputs by project partners. As such, it embeds multiple sources and points of view to ensure that shared and consolidated conclusions are drawn with respect to such a complex theme, as the case of replicability.

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1 CRITERIA FOR REPLICABILITY OF VALUE CHAINS AT NATIONAL SCALE

This chapter analyses the replicability of the CIRCPACK value chains within European Countries. The analysis is structured into two subsequent steps:

- qualitative analysis based on the CEIS indicators, valid transversally for all the value-chains;
- quantitative tailored analysis at value chain level, depending on the intrinsic features of each value chain in terms of LCA results.

1.1 REPLICABILITY ANALYSIS BASED ON CEIS

The CEIS set of indicators is used in the CIRCPACK project to analyse from a comprehensive perspective the performance of the value chains.

The CEIS framework of indicators is specifically proposed in the methodological document D2.2 "Methodology for CIRC-PACK" value chains evaluation and then applied in D2.3 "State of play of the demo case using the CEIS".

For this preliminary analysis, among all the indicators included within the wide CEIS framework, those parameters included in the life cycle inventories are considered. To this purpose, the most available set of consistent data across all the European Countries is represented by the Circular Economy Indicators published on Eurostat to monitor the progress of circular economy within Member States, coupled with specific data for plastic packaging materials.

The screening which can be obtained as a result of such analysis provides an overview of objective high-scale data – applicable to all the value chains – that are a proxy of the status of advancement of circular economy in a country, mainly based on general parameters, representing the state-of-art.

It is implicitly assumed that if a positive quantitative performance is monitored, the boundary conditions for the implementation of circular economy schemes are overall favourable, from multiple perspectives.

Starting with the carried out analysis, six indicators were identified, which are useful to determine the degree of circular economy application in the individual European countries.

The selected indicators are:

- **recycling rate of plastic packaging - material indicator** (Eurostat, CEI_WM020): it represents the percentage of recycled plastic packaging waste in all generated plastic packaging waste. Considered data refer generally to the year 2017, but some different choices have been made, based on data availability;
- **circular material use rate - material indicator** (Eurostat, CEI_SRM030): it represents the percentage value of secondary materials use as a substitute for primary raw materials. As for the previous indicator, considered data refer generally to the year 2017, but some different choices have been made, based on data availability;

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- **number of patents related to recycling and secondary raw materials - R&D indicator** (Eurostat, CEI_CIE020): it provides a measure of innovation, which plays a key role in the transition towards a circular economy, in the development of new technologies, processes, services and business models. Considered data refer to 2015, the most recent year for which information is available;
- **value added at factor cost - economic indicator** (Eurostat, CEI_CIE010): with reference to the recycling, repair and reuse and rental and leasing sectors, this indicator represents the gross income from operating activities after adjusting for operating subsidies and indirect taxes, thus representing a measure of net income deriving from the aforementioned activities. In this specific case, the differential percentage between the two years 2013 and 2017 has been calculated, in order to analyse the performance of the trend (i.e.: increasing, decreasing or stable trend), rather than its absolute value;
- **gross investment in tangible goods - economic indicator** (Eurostat, CEI_CIE010): with reference to the recycling, repair and reuse and rental and leasing sectors, this indicator is defined as investment during the reference year in all tangible goods. As for the previous indicator, the differential percentage between the two years 2013 and 2017 has been calculated, in order to understand its increasing, decreasing or stable trend;
- **person employed - social indicator** (Eurostat, CEI_CIE010): with reference to the recycling, repair and reuse and rental and leasing sectors, this indicator provides a measure of the quantity of offered jobs. Also in this case, the differential percentage between the two years 2013 and 2017 has been calculated, in order to understand its increasing, decreasing or stable trend.

It is important to underline the presence of rental and leasing as sectors included in the last three indicators is not directly related to the context of circular economy and it may slightly affect the overall conclusions.

Furthermore, in order to simplify the analysis, the first two indicators have been grouped under the label of material indicators, the third one has been defined as R&D indicator, the fourth and fifth indicators have been called economic indicators and finally, the sixth one has been considered as a social indicator.

The following Table 1 illustrates the indicators value for each European country.

As it can be seen, three colours were assigned to the values of the considered indicators: yellow, green and red. These colours make visible the assessment of potential replicability based on the values retrieved. Such assessment is carried out based on a benchmark for introduced for each indicator.

The yellow colour, an index of moderation, has been used for values within the intermediate range, determined as plus/minus 20% of the benchmark, for almost all the indicators; the green colour, an index of positivity, has been used for higher values than the intermediate range; while the red colour, an index of negativity, has been used for lower values than the intermediate range.

As just mentioned, a benchmark has been identified for each indicator, in order to evaluate the performance of each Country towards potential replicability. Firstly, considering the

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Recycling rate of plastic packaging indicator, there are two established benchmarks, used to define the intermediate range boundaries: the European countries average value, given by Eurostat database and the 2030 European target for plastic packaging (55%); secondly, with regard of the Circular material use rate indicator, the used benchmark results the European countries average value, given by Eurostat database; thirdly, considering the R&D indicator, the defined benchmark results the European countries average value, calculated as arithmetic average; finally, for both the economic and social indicators, the benchmark has been identified on the basis of European values provided by Eurostat.

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Table 1: Indicators value for each European Country

Countries/Indicators	Material Indicators		R&D Indicator	Economic Indicators		Social Indicator
	Recycling rate of plastic packaging [%]	Circular material use rate [%]	Number of patents related to recycling and secondary raw materials	Value added at factor cost [%]	Gross investment in tangible goods [%]	Persons employed [%]
EU	41.9	11.7	15.5	0.17	0.26	0.04
Belgium	44.5	17.8	8.91	0.12	0.07	0.02
Bulgaria	64.8	5.1	-	0.45	-0.14	-0.03
Czechia	58.9	8.1	9.58	NA	NA	NA
Denmark	38.5	8	4.65	0.15	0.29	0.1
Germany	48	11.6	89.87	0.22	0.32	0.13
Estonia	26.5	8.7	-	0.37	-0.2	0.19
Ireland	30.5	1.6	1.5	NA	NA	NA
Greece	41.4	2.4	1	-0.1	0.4	0.18
Spain	47.9	7.4	19.82	0	0.49	0.17
France	26.5	18.6	36.68	0.06	0.07	0.01
Croatia	37.3	5.1	-	0.2	-0.35	0.1
Italy	42.4	17.7	18.91	0.1	0.26	0.02
Cyprus	62.3	2.2	1.5	0.39	1.33	0.32
Latvia	36.6	6.6	2.5	0.27	0.85	0.04
Lithuania	74.2	4.8	-	0.46	0.53	0.05
Luxembourg	33.4	8.9	2	NA	NA	NA
Hungary	32	6.6	1.33	0.61	0.5	0.19
Malta	23.5	6.7	1	NA	NA	NA

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Countries/Indicators	Material Indicators		R&D Indicator	Economic Indicators		Social Indicator
	Recycling rate of plastic packaging [%]	Circular material use rate [%]	Number of patents related to recycling and secondary raw materials	Value added at factor cost [%]	Gross investment in tangible goods [%]	Persons employed [%]
Netherlands	50.4	29.9	20.9	0.19	0.35	0.05
Austria	33.4	11.6	8.22	0.31	0.12	0.04
Poland	34.6	9.5	67.4	0.23	0.12	0.06
Portugal	34.9	1.8	5	0.31	0.35	0.12
Romania	46.5	1.8	4.5	0.52	0.33	-0.02
Slovenia	60.4	8.5	-	0.22	NA	0.01
Slovakia	52.4	5.1	6.2	0.14	0.85	0.06
Finland	26.5	2.2	16.46	0.02	0.01	-0.08
Sweden	48.4	6.5	9.81	-0.14	-0.04	0.08
United Kingdom	46.2	17.8	17.88	0.21	NA	0.03

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In view of the final purpose of assessing the replicability potential in European Countries, based on the status of advancement of circular economy, five clusters of countries have been identified, based on the context level of positivity or negativity, determined by the indicators value. The group of 28 European countries (2013-2020) has been classified into five subgroups outlined as very positive (VP), positive (P), moderate (M), negative (N) and not defined (ND), based on the overall performance assessed. The general subdivision criteria are shown below.

- **Very Positive (VP):** the majority of indicators is green and no red performance is registered;
- **Positive (P):** there are green/yellow colours for at least one indicator for each grouping labels (Material Indicators, R&D Indicator, Economic Indicators, Social Indicator);
- **Moderate (M):** there are green/yellow colours for at least one indicator for each of the two grouping labels Material Indicators and R&D Indicator and not negative values (signal of a decreasing trend) for the other two grouping labels Economic Indicators and Social Indicator;
- **Negative (N):** almost all indicator values are red/yellow;
- **Not defined (ND):** there is a large presence of not available data (NA) and in particular they are part of the same grouping labels.

Based on the criteria just presented, the five identified groups of countries are illustrated below through Table 2.

It is important to underline that when the belonging of a Country to a cluster is ambiguous, the choice of the cluster has been based not only on the established criteria, but has been also forced through considerations based on the priority of some indicators over others (e.g. the indicator Recycling rate of plastic packaging is more specific for plastic packaging and thus has higher weight).

Table 2: Status of advancement of circular economy within the various European countries

Cluster	Countries
VP	Germany and Netherlands
P	Spain, Italy, United Kingdom
M	Belgium, Cyprus, Lithuania, Denmark, France, Latvia, Austria, Poland, Portugal, Slovenia Slovakia,
N	Bulgaria, Estonia, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Romania, Finland, Sweden
ND	Czechia, Ireland, Luxembourg, Malta

Summarizing the results, the clusters including the highest number of Countries are the moderate and the negative, with eight countries each. The number of countries decreases with the positive cluster, comprising six countries, and with the very positive cluster, which has only two countries. Moreover, it was not possible to attribute a circular economy level to four countries, due to the lack of useful information for the analysis.

Based on the proposed analysis, identifying the European Countries with a positive or very positive performance with respect to the level of implementation of circular economy, it is possible to preliminary identify potential areas for replicability and establishment of circular

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value chains in the plastic packaging. The elected indicators are indeed a proxy for the assessment of the current operating framework in the circular economy. As a result, countries belonging to the very positive and positive cluster can be considered as more suitable for the implementation and replication of CIRCPACK findings and products.

1.2 REPLICABILITY ANALYSIS BASED ON LCA RESULTS

In this section, the influence of quantitative national factors is evaluated varying the most influencing parameters of the results of the CEIS assessments and LCA in particular carried out on the improved value chains, within the framework of WP2.

In detail, for each value chain, national based factors are firstly identified, and then are varied in ranges of values selected based on the expected performance of different European Countries. The calculation for coffee capsules value chain has only been performed as a preliminary analysis in collaboration with NOVAMONT. Results are under evaluation and they will be reported in the Final Technical Report.

Overall, the national based factors considered as relevant for this analysis, coherently also with the detail of the CEIS assessment performed, are:

- electricity mix;
- End-of-Life treatment.

The effect of varying these factors depends mainly on the influence of the parameters on the overall life cycle performance and also on the ranges in which the parameters vary in the European context. It is also specified that the variation of the electricity mix is referred only to the processes characterizing the specific values and, as a result, electricity consumption related to material manufacturing is not always accounted. This aspect will be highlighted from case to case, and each assumption is mainly based on the presentation of the value chains within D2.4.

For the analysis of the influence of **electricity mix**, the baseline assessment is performed with average European electricity mix (note: this does not represent the real mix for the manufacturing processes in CIRCPACK). In order to understand the influence of relying on different energy mixes, two scenarios are considered:

- worst case scenario, which is modelled by using the electricity mix with the highest emission factor for GWP impact category, according to the default emission factors provided by the Covenant of Mayors on LCA basis (Koffi et al.; 2017);
- best case scenario, which is modelled by using the electricity mix with the lowest emission factor for GWP impact category, according to the default emission factors provided by the Covenant of Mayors on LCA basis (Koffi et al.; 2017).

Table 3 reports the environmental performances of the aforementioned electricity mixes.

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Table 3. Impacts of Electricity Mixes (1 kWh)

Impact Category	Unit	Baseline	Best case	Worst case
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	0.464	0.041	0.883
Ozone formation, Human health	kg NO _x eq	0.001	0.000	0.003
Ozone formation, Terrestrial ecosystems	kg NO _x eq	0.001	0.000	0.003
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	0.002	0.000	0.006
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	0.116	0.008	0.276
Water consumption	m ³	0.007	0.006	0.005

It is highlighted that it cannot be straightforwardly assumed that all the other indicators for the selected mixes represent boundary values for the European context, even if many are related to the performance obtained in terms of GWP.

In addition, the influence of the **cost of electricity supply** on the OPEX costs for each value chain is also studied. For this analysis, the following scenarios are assumed:

- baseline scenario: electricity cost of 0.10 €/kWh
- best case scenario: electricity cost of 0.06 €/kWh;
- worst case scenario: electricity cost of 0.15 €/kWh.

In detail, the value for the baseline scenario is assumed as given in D2.4, while the values for best case and worst case scenarios are extracted from the Eurostat database (Eurostat, NRG_PC_205).

For the analysis of the influence of different **EoL treatments**, the recycling rate is considered as the most significant national based indicator. Thus, three scenarios (baseline, best case and worst case) are defined according to the recycling rate, as main indicator and, consequently, to associated recovery and landfill rates.

The baseline scenario is represented by the average European recycling rate for the packaging material associated with each value chain. In order to understand the influence of relying on different packaging recycling rates, two additional scenarios are considered:

- worst case scenario, which is identified on the basis of the lowest recycling rate among the European countries;
- best case scenario, which is identified on the basis of the highest recycling rate among the European countries.

It is important to specify that for the EoL treatment analysis, Eurostat data about plastic and paper/cardboard packaging End-of-Life treatments rate are used as references. Three treatment typologies have been selected and their definitions are illustrated below, based on the provisions of the Waste Framework Directive 2008/98/EC, amended by Directive (EU) 2018/85, as fundamental basis:

- landfill: deposit into or on to land (disposal operation D1);
- incineration: both use principally as a fuel or other means to generate energy (recovery operation R1) and incineration on land (disposal operation D10);

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- recycling: both recycling/reclamation of organic substances which are not used as solvents (recovery operation R3) and recycling/reclamation of other inorganic materials (recovery operation R5).

The types of packaging materials included are paper/cardboard packaging (applicable to multimaterial packaging for power detergent value chain) and plastic packaging (applicable to the other value chains). It is important to underline that plastic packaging recycling rate is a general indicator for plastic packaging overall context and not specific for each type of packaging selected within the project. Even if the indicator is not directly related to the context of circular economy for every specific packaging, it is considered as a representative aspect for a high level evaluation.

Table 4 gives visibility to recycling rate of paper/cardboard packaging and plastic packaging (Eurostat, CEI_WM020), showing a comparison between the defined baseline and the worst and best cases, and their relative variation with respect to the baseline case.

In order to clearly interpret the following calculations performed, it is important to specify that for the EoL treatment analysis, the labels “baseline”, “best” and “worst” – used for the definition of the scenarios - are assigned based on the sole recycling rate, excluding the performance in terms of landfill and energy recovery. For this reason, the environmental performance may not reflect the trend of the correspondent scenario for all the indicators, as also the values of landfill and recycling affect this parameter.

Table 4. Percentage of recycling rates for paper/cardboard and plastic packaging

Packaging Material	Unit	EU average	Best case		Worst case	
			Abs.	Variation	Abs.	Variation
Paper/cardboard	%	84.7	99.7	18%	59.7	-42%
Plastic	%	41.9	74.2	77%	23.5	-78%

Then, in order to fully characterize the scenarios previously introduced, the incineration and landfill rates (Eurostat, CEI_WM020) are presented in Table 5. Considering that the recycling rate is selected as the most relevant indicator, these additional rates may not represent extreme values in the European context, but they merely represent the incineration and landfill rates associated with the average, highest and lowest recycling rates. Recycling percentages are the same illustrated in the previous table. They are repeated just to give more fluence to the calculation logical flow.

Table 5. Percentage of EoL treatments for paper/cardboard and plastic packaging

Indicator	Unit	Paper/cardboard packaging			Plastic packaging		
		EU average	Best case	Worst case	EU average	Best case	Worst case
Recycling rate	%	84.7	99.7	59.7	41.9	74.2	23.5
Incineration rate	%	7.2	0	0.1	33	1.5	0.2
Landfill rate	%	8.1	0.3	40.2	25.1	24.3	76.3

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1.2.1 MULTIMATERIAL PACKAGING FOR POWDER DETERGENT VALUE CHAIN

Powder detergent boxes are one of the products improved by CIRC-PACK project. The final product manufacturing can be summarized into two separate stages: box manufacturing and box filling with detergent. The main changes due to CIRC-PACK's innovations take place in the box manufacturing stage, since other raw materials are used. While in the baseline, a polystyrene layer were used to provide barrier properties to the box, a new innovative material based on paper and a biobased dispersion coating has been developed during the project and validated as material.

1.2.1.1 Influence of Electricity mix

Based on the results of the LCA for this CIRCPACK value chain, it appears that electricity consumption for box manufacturing contributes to the 83% of the total Global Warming Indicator calculated for the value chain, resulting as a key factor for the performance of the chain.

Table 6 summarizes the influence of different electricity mixes on the performance of the powder detergent value chain, based on data for one box.

Table 6. Influence of Electricity mix on Powder Detergent value chain

Impact Category	Best case	Worst case
Global warming	-76%	75%
Ozone formation, Human health	-69%	232%
Ozone formation, Terrestrial ecosystems	-69%	232%
Terrestrial acidification	-44%	102%
Fossil resource scarcity	-76%	113%
Water consumption	-14%	-30%

It can be observed that for GWP, a symmetrical deviation of 75% with respect to the baseline performance can be expected. Fossil resource scarcity is associated with a variation in the same order of magnitude of GWP in positive terms, and slightly higher in negative. Moreover, ozone formation (health and terrestrial) improves of almost 70% in the best scenario, while an increase of the same impacts of over 200% is registered in the worst-case scenario. Finally, water consumption presents a decrease in both scenarios, highlighting that the energy mixes selected do not represent best case and worst case for all the indicators.

Table 8 summarizes the influence of different electricity supply costs on the OPEX cost for manufacturing a powder detergent box.

Table 7. Influence of Electricity cost on Powder Detergent value chain

Parameter	Best case	Worst-case
OPEX	-31%	38%

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It can be observed that the influence of electricity cost on the OPEX for one box is significant. A low cost of electricity supply can lead to savings in the order of 30% of the baseline OPEX, while a high electricity cost can increase the OPEX of about 40%. This result is given by the fact that – as shown in D2.4 - electricity cost represents a significant share of the OPEX, being the inventory flow that its majorly contributes to the total value at box scale.

1.2.1.2 Influence of Recycling rate

On the basis of the treatment typologies percentages in Europe for paper/cardboard packaging (Eurostat data) and the results of the LCA for this CIRCPACK value chain calculated in D2.4 considering different End-of-Life treatments for paper/cardboard packaging, values of the chosen impact categories have been calculated.

Table 8 summarizes the influence of different EoL treatments mixes on the performance of the powder detergent value chain.

Table 8. Influence of EoL treatments on power detergent value chain

Impact Category	Best case	Worst case
Global warming	-5%	14%
Ozone formation, Human health	-10%	14%
Ozone formation, Terrestrial ecosystems	-10%	14%
Terrestrial acidification	-4%	6%
Fossil resource scarcity	-3%	5%
Water consumption	0%	0%

It can be observed that GWP improves of 5% in the best scenario, while an increase of the same impacts of 14% in registered in the worst-case scenario.

Considering the other impact categories, excluding water consumption, an almost symmetrical deviation with respect to the baseline performance can be expected. Finally, water consumption is not affected by the variation of the EoL treatments mix.

1.2.2 PLASTIC PACKAGING FOR LIQUID SHAMPOO VALUE CHAIN

Most bottles for liquid detergent products are based on HPDE or PET and are prepared by blowing plastic preforms previously generated by injection moulding. Regarding the bottle caps, they are usually based on PP and produced by injection moulding. Regarding its EoL, PET bottles have an average recycling rate in Europe of 40 %. On the other hand, PP caps are normally landfilled because they are discarded in the first steps of sorting processes due to its small size, ending up in the plants' rejected fraction.

Within the CIRCPACK project, the use of bioplastics to manufacture shampoo bottles was validated, reducing the fossil plastic dependence in the sector and allowing compostability and biodegradability.

1.2.2.1 Influence of Electricity mix

Based on the results of the LCA for this CIRCPACK value chain, it appears that electricity consumption generated by extrusion and blow moulding processes contributes to

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approximately 45% of the total Global Warming Indicator calculated for the value chain, resulting as a relevant for the performance of the chain, after the material manufacturing processes.

The analysis is performed as already presented in the previous paragraph, and the results are shown in Table 9 below, for a single shampoo bottle. It is highlighted that the variation of impacts from occurring electricity consumption during raw material production is not accounted.

Table 9. Influence of Electricity mix on Liquid Shampoo value chain

Impact Category	Best case	Worst case
Global warming	-26%	25%
Ozone formation, Human health	-21%	69%
Ozone formation, Terrestrial ecosystems	-20%	67%
Terrestrial acidification	0%	0%
Fossil resource scarcity	-17%	26%
Water consumption	-5%	-12%

As expected, the pattern of the results obtained are similar to the previous case, considering that the same parameter is varied. The fact that different shares of benefits or disadvantages are obtained depends on the influence of the electricity mix on the performance across all the impacts category.

It can be observed that for GWP, an almost symmetrical deviation of 25% with respect to the baseline performance can be expected, while acidification is not affected by the variation of the mix. Moreover, ozone formation (health and terrestrial) improves of 20% in the best scenario, while an increase of the same impacts of 70% is registered in the worst-case scenario. Finally, for fossil resource scarcity shows slight variations, of 17% in the best-case scenario and 26% in the worst case scenario; water consumption presents a slight decrease in both scenarios.

Table 8 summarizes the influence of different electricity supply costs on the OPEX cost for manufacturing a shampoo bottle, under the scenario +10% according to D2.4. As in previous case, it is highlighted that the occurring cost of electricity embedded in the cost of raw material production is not varied.

Table 10. Influence of Electricity cost on Liquid Shampoo value chain

Parameter	Best case	Worst case
OPEX	-6%	8%

It can be observed that the influence of electricity cost on the OPEX for one bottle is limited, but non negligible. Indeed, a low cost of electricity supply can lead to savings in the order of 6% of the baseline OPEX, while a high electricity cost can increase the OPEX of about 8%. This result is given by the fact that – as shown in D2.4 – the major cost contributing to the OPEX of this value chain is given by the raw material.

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1.2.2.2 Influence of Recycling rate

On the basis of the treatment typologies percentages in Europe for plastic packaging (Eurostat data) and the results of the LCA for this CIRCPACK value chain considering different End-of-Life treatments, values of the chosen impact categories have been calculated, with a focus on three scenarios (baseline, best case and worst case) defined bases on the recycling plastic packaging indicator.

Table 11 summarizes the influence of different EoL treatments mixes on the performance of the liquid shampoo value chain. For this value chain, the EoL route including composting has not been included, due to difficulty in extrapolating the composting rate from existing statistics.

Table 11. Influence of EoL treatments on liquid shampoo value chain

Impact Category	Best case	Worst case
Global warming	-1%	33%
Ozone formation, Human health	-1%	41%
Ozone formation, Terrestrial ecosystems	-1%	41%
Terrestrial acidification	-1%	61%
Fossil resource scarcity	-1%	53%
Water consumption	-0.2%	14%

It can be observed a not very relevant improvement from the baseline to the best case (1% for all impact categories, except for water consumption that increases of 0.2%), while important decreases of environmental performance characterize the worst cases, from the highest 61% of terrestrial acidification to the lowest 14% of water consumption.

1.2.3 PLASTIC SHOPPING BAGS VALUE CHAIN

This value chain covers the production of bio-based biodegradable and compostable thin and thick shopping bags. Being the manufacturing processes equivalent, and proportional to weight, only the thin bags are considered in the following analysis. The results that can be calculated for the thick bags are proportional. The manufacturing process from the raw biopolymer includes film extrusion, welding and sealing.

1.2.3.1 Influence of Electricity mix

Based on the results of the LCA for this CIRCPACK value chain, it appears that electricity consumption generated by bag extrusion, welding and sealing represents approximately 24%-45% of life cycle impacts, being the second major contributor after raw materials.

The analysis is performed as already presented in the previous paragraph, and the results are shown in Table 12 below, for one bag. It is highlighted that the variation of impacts from occurring electricity consumption during raw material production are not accounted.

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Table 12. Influence of Electricity mix on Plastic Shopping Bags value chain

Impact Category	Best case	Worst case
Global warming	-13%	13%
Ozone formation, Human health	-9%	31%
Ozone formation, Terrestrial ecosystems	-9%	30%
Terrestrial acidification	-11%	25%
Fossil resource scarcity	-8%	12%
Water consumption	-3%	-8%

It can be observed that for GWP, a symmetrical deviation of 13% with respect to the baseline performance can be expected. As for the ozone formation impact category (human health and terrestrial ecosystems), benefits and negative effects are unbalanced: in the best case scenario, and improvement of 9% is obtained, while negative effects are higher in relative terms, being about 30%. A similar trend is calculated for terrestrial acidification.

Fossil resource scarcity impact category is slightly affected, similarly to the case of GWP. Finally, as in the other cases, water consumption presents a slight decrease in both scenarios.

Table 16 summarizes the influence of different electricity supply costs on the OPEX cost for manufacturing thin bag, under the single scenario according to D2.4. As in previous case, it is highlighted that the occurring cost of electricity embedded in the cost of raw material production is not varied.

Table 13. Influence of Electricity cost on Shopping Bags value chain

Parameter	Best case	Worst case
OPEX	-3%	3%

It can be observed that the influence of electricity cost on the OPEX for one bottle is limited. This result is given by the fact that – as shown in D2.4 – the major cost contributing to the OPEX of this value chain is given by the raw material, representing almost 90% of the total OPEX.

1.2.3.2 Influence of Recycling rate

The influence of different EoL treatments mixes on the performance of shopping plastic bags value chain is shown in Table 14 below. It is calculated based on the methodology described in section 1.2.

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Table 14. Influence of EoL treatments on plastic shopping bags value chain

Impact Category	Best case	Worst case
Global warming	-114%	-14%
Ozone formation, Human health	-98%	21%
Ozone formation, Terrestrial ecosystems	-101%	22%
Terrestrial acidification	-83%	24%
Fossil resource scarcity	-119%	31%
Water consumption	-29%	6%

It can be observed a very relevant improvement from the baseline to the best case, ranging from 83% to more than 100%. Water consumption is an exception, with a decrease of 29%. Considering the worst case, there is an increase of the values with respect to the baseline performance for all the impact categories, with the exclusion of GWP that presents a decrease of 14%, due to the highest impact of incineration compared to landfill.

1.2.4 FOOD PACKAGING (TRAYS AND MULTILAYER FILM) VALUE CHAIN

This value chain represents the usual food packaging consisting on a plastic tray sealed with a plastic film. The CIRC-PACK value chain takes as demonstrator a chicken meat pack containing an average of 850 g of chicken meat. The packaging is made up of a PET tray and a PET/PE covering multilayer film. The product brand owner buys thermoformed PET trays and rolled blown-film and packages the meat in trays while injecting a combination of inert gases to extend the shelf-life of the product. The CIRCPACK innovation relies on the replacement of the fossil-based plastic materials by biodegradable and compostable bioplastic.

1.2.4.1 Influence of Electricity mix

Based on the results of the LCA analysis for this CIRCPACK value chain, the processes associated with electricity consumption are film extrusion and thermoforming of the trays, from the virgin biopolymer. It should be highlighted that as far as the total impacts are concerned, trays represent by far the most relevant contributors to the environmental impacts of each packaging unit.

The results of the analysis are shown in Table 15 below, for one packaging unit. They are calculated based on the methodology described in section 1.2. It is highlighted that the variation of impacts from occurring electricity consumption during raw material production are not accounted.

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Table 15. Influence of Electricity mix on Food Packaging value chain

Impact Category	Best case	Worst case
Global warming	-50%	49%
Ozone formation, Human health	-40%	135%
Ozone formation, Terrestrial ecosystems	-40%	134%
Terrestrial acidification	-47%	109%
Fossil resource scarcity	-41%	61%
Water consumption	-11%	-23%

For this value chain, it is observed that the variation of the electricity mix leads to significant effects on the environmental performance of the value chain.

In terms of GWP, a symmetric deviation of about 50% is estimated. For ozone formation (human health and terrestrial ecosystems) and terrestrial acidification, benefits exceeds 40% in the best case, while negative effects largely exceed 100% in the worst-case scenario. Finally, the patterns obtained for fossil resource scarcity and water consumption are also coherent with results previously obtained: the first category is not affected by the variation of energy mix; the second is coherent with the variation of GWP, presenting achievable benefits of 40% and potential negative effects of maximum 60%; the last one is always associated with beneficial effects (do to the specific electricity mixes selected).

For this value chain, the OPEX is estimated based on materials costs in D2.4, due to data availability. For this reason, the assessment is not performed.

1.2.4.2 Influence of Recycling rate

The influence of different EoL treatments mixes on the performance of food packaging value chain is shown in Table 16 below. It is calculated based on the methodology described in section 1.2.

However, it is highlighted that recycling of the food packaging may have some limitations, as recycling biopolymers is possible, but organic carbon chains degrade faster under some conditions, and the quality of the recycled material is lower. In addition, manufacturers advise to limit the number of recycling cycles to just one. Also, to keep the functionality of the final material, it has been tested that a maximum amount of recycled material in the raw material compound of 30 % is feasible (validated for carrier bags' film manufacturing).

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Table 16. Influence of EoL treatments for food packaging value chain

Impact Category	Best case	Worst case
Global warming	-37%	-12%
Ozone formation, Human health	-28%	11%
Ozone formation, Terrestrial ecosystems	-28%	11%
Terrestrial acidification	-27%	11%
Fossil resource scarcity	-31%	17%
Water consumption	-23%	6%

It appears that a high recycling rate leads to an improvement of the environmental performance across all the impact categories, ranging from 20% to 40% with respect to the baseline scenario. In case a low recycling rate is accounted, the performance decreases across all the impact categories from 5% to 20%, with the exception of global warming potential, which still presents an improvement in comparison to the baseline case, due to the fact that the recovery process is most impactful than landfilling, under the assumptions made for the analysis.

1.2.5 PLASTIC AUTOMOTIVE COMPONENTS VALUE CHAIN

In the traditional chain, air ducts and bumpers are based on plastic materials (polypropylene) including several additives. These automotive components are produced by injection moulding from already prepared masterbatches of the plastic material with the corresponding reinforcement. Within the CIRCPACK project, several attempts to improve the recycled content into automotive plastic components were assessed.

1.2.5.1 Influence of Electricity mix

For this value chain, a number of different CIRCPACK scenarios is investigated within D2.4, depending on assumptions about scraps treatment, EoL management or transportations. In order to assess the influence of varying the electricity mix on the environmental performance, two of these scenarios are selected:

- Scenario 2 – best environmental performance: as most relevant feature, it foresees the Reuse of the recycled material (bumpers and air ducts scraps) for internal automotive recycling;
- Scenario 4 – among the scenarios with the highest electricity consumptions, it is the one with the best environmental performance: this scenario considers that all processes developed for scrap treatments are held in CRF plant.

The analysis is carried out based on the methodology described in section 1.2, and the results are shown in Table 17 for Scenario 2 and Scenario 4, respectively. The functional unit is 1 kg of final product (air duct/bumper).

In general terms, it is clear that for the case of Scenario 2, the variation of electricity mix does not lead to significant variation of the overall performance, possibly to the low amount of electricity requested for this Scenario. On the other hand, for Scenario 4 the impact of varying the electricity mix is notable.

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Table 17. Influence of Electricity mix on Automotive Components value chain

Impact Category	Best case – Scenario 2	Worst case – Scenario 2	Best case – Scenario 4	Worst case – Scenario 4
Global warming	-3%	3%	-70%	69%
Ozone formation, Human health	-3%	10%	-64%	213%
Ozone formation, Terrestrial ecosystems	-3%	10%	-62%	210%
Terrestrial acidification	-4%	9%	-77%	179%
Fossil resource scarcity	-2%	4%	-52%	77%
Water consumption	-1%	-1%	-12%	-27%

For Scenario 2, for all the environmental categories, relative influence does not exceed 4% in terms of benefits, and of 10% in terms of negative effects. The trend is correspondent to those already encountered in previous analyses.

For Scenario 4, the variation of the electricity mix leads to significant effects on the environmental performance of the value chain.

In terms of GWP, a symmetric deviation of about 70% is estimated. For ozone formation (human health and terrestrial ecosystems) and terrestrial acidification, benefits exceeds 60% in the best case, while negative effects even exceed 200% in the worst-case scenario. Finally, the patterns obtained for fossil resource scarcity and water consumption are also coherent with results previously obtained: the first category is minimally affected by the variation of energy mix; the second is coherent with the variation of GWP, presenting achievable benefits of 50% and potential negative effects of maximum approximately 80%; the last one is always associated with beneficial effects (do to the specific electricity mixes selected).

For the evaluation of the influence of electricity cost on the OPEX costs for the automotive components value chain, scenario 1 as for D2.4 is selected as reference, as it is common also to all the other scenarios developed.

Thus, Table 18 summarizes the influence of different electricity supply costs on the OPEX cost for scrap generation, under the single scenario according to D2.4. As in previous case, it is highlighted that the occurring cost of electricity embedded in the cost of raw material production is not varied.

Table 18. Influence of Electricity cost on Automotive Components value chain – Scenario 1

Parameter	Best case	Worst case
OPEX	-40%	50%

It can be observed that the influence of electricity cost on the scrap manufacturing by grinding is significant and it ranges from 40% in positive terms to 50% in negative terms. This is related to the fact that electricity and oil are the only flows contributing to the OPEX costs of a grinder, but it is worth highlighting that for such process, annual CAPEX associated with grinding equipment can be more than double than the OPEX.

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1.2.5.2 Influence of Recycling rate

For this value chain, the recycling of plastic production scraps is managed at company/industrial level and thus it cannot be considered as a national-based factor influencing the performance of the value chain. For this reason, an analysis based on the variation of the recycling rate and other end-of-life options is not carried out.

1.2.6 ABSORBENT HYGIENE PRODUCTS (AHPs) VALUE CHAIN

The baseline scenario of the Absorbent Hygiene Products (AHP) value chain foresees the production of following packaging items from virgin materials (PE, PP and wood, respectively): i) Secondary packaging of AHPs (PE film), ii) Plastic boxes used as tertiary packaging of diapers (PP boxes) and iii) wood mini-pallets for product distribution (wood mini-pallet), including the recycling process of post-consumer AHP waste, where cellulose, SAP and plastic are obtained as main outputs. Within the CIRCPACK project, the recycled plastic fraction (85% PP, 15% PE as average composition of the AHP recycled plastic as it comes out of the treatment plant) from post-consumer AHP waste is used for the production of plastic boxes and mini-pallets (avoiding consumption of virgin materials). On the other hand, the recycled cellulose is used as raw material for biomaterials manufactured by NOVAMONT.

1.2.6.1 Influence of Electricity mix

As mentioned in the previous description of the value chain, a key process for the entire circularity chain is the recycling of AHPs, which is thus considered as the relevant process for this analysis. In addition, the mass of waste treated (i.e.: 1 kg) is considered as the reference unit for this analysis: this choice also allows to avoid introducing allocation schemes to assign overall impacts to the multiple end products of the recycling process, namely plastic boxes and mini-pallets, guaranteeing a higher transparency for the result.

The analysis is performed as already presented in the previous paragraph, and the results are shown in Table 19 below.

Table 19. Influence of Electricity mix on the recycling of AHPs value chain – Scenario 2

Impact Category	Best case	Worst case
Global warming	-12%	12%
Ozone formation, Human health	-10%	32%
Ozone formation, Terrestrial ecosystems	-9%	31%
Terrestrial acidification	-11%	25%
Fossil resource scarcity	-4%	6%
Water consumption	-5%	-10%

For this value chain, the variation of the electricity mix entails visible effects on the environmental performance of the recycling process.

In terms of GWP, a symmetric deviation of about 12% is estimated. For ozone formation (human health and terrestrial ecosystems) and terrestrial acidification, benefits exceeds 10% in the best case, while negative are in the order of 32% in the worst-case scenario. Finally,

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the patterns obtained for fossil resource scarcity and water consumption are also coherent with results previously obtained: the first category is minimally affected by the variation of energy mix; the second is coherent with the variation of GWP, presenting an almost symmetrical variation in the order of 5%; the last one is always associated with beneficial effects (do to the specific electricity mixes selected).

For the evaluation of the influence of electricity cost on the OPEX costs for the recycling of AHPs products, it is assumed that the overall OPEX cost for the recycling plant, as for the contents of D2.4, takes into account an electricity consumption of 200 kWh/t of waste processed, purchased at average Italian electricity cost. On this basis, the baseline scenario, characterized by average EU electricity cost is built, and deviations in best case and worst case are calculated.

Table 20 summarizes the results of this analysis.

Table 20. Influence of Electricity cost on the recycling of AHPs value chain

Parameter	Best case	Worst case
OPEX	-7%	9%

It can be observed that the influence of electricity cost on the overall OPEX of the plant is of 7% in terms of achievable savings and of 9% in terms of potential additional costs. These percentages are quite significant especially if considering that the OPEX value used for the calculation is the overall OPEX of the recycling plant (and not of a specific process or equipment).

1.2.6.2 Influence of Recycling rate

The analysis is performed as already presented in the previous paragraphs, and the influence of different EoL treatments on the performance of the products featuring the AHPs value chain is shown in Table 21 for secondary packaging, Table 22 for pamper boxes and Table 23 for mini-pallets. It is highlighted that the analysis is not focused on the innovation itself, which is the recycling process of AHPs, but it is referred to ordinary waste management of the products manufactured from the secondary raw materials.

The composting route, which is embedded in the recycling rates presented and which is applicable to secondary packaging for AHPs product is not considered in this assessment, due to limited availability of specific data, likely associated with a very low share of composting for biodegradable plastic packaging.

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Table 21. Influence of EoL treatments on AHPs value chain – Secondary Packaging

Impact Category	Best case	Worst case
Global warming	-49%	-13%
Ozone formation, Human health	-40%	17%
Ozone formation, Terrestrial ecosystems	-41%	18%
Terrestrial acidification	-38%	20%
Fossil resource scarcity	-40%	23%
Water consumption	-13%	3%

The variation of the EoL scenario leads to significant effects on the environmental performance of secondary packaging produced from recovered AHPs. For all the indicators, except for global warming potential, an increase of the recycling rate leads to an improvement of the performance, in the order of 40% for ozone formation (human health and terrestrial), acidification, fossil resource scarcity and of about 15% in terms of water consumption. Conversely, an increase of the recycling rate is associated with a worsen in the order of 20% with respect to baseline, expect for water consumption which is only slightly affected. Finally, as for global warming potential, in both worst and best case scenarios, the performance improves with respect to the baseline case, due to the fact that under the assumptions of the study, landfill presents a lower global warming potential than incineration.

Table 22. Influence of EoL treatments on AHPs value chain – Pamper Boxes

Impact Category	Best case	Worst case
Global warming	-134%	-48%
Ozone formation, Human health	-31%	12%
Ozone formation, Terrestrial ecosystems	-34%	14%
Terrestrial acidification	-16%	8%
Fossil resource scarcity	-93%	53%
Water consumption	-21%	12%

For the case of pamper boxes obtained from recycling AHPs products, the influence of different scenarios of EoL treatments, with specific reference to the recycling rate is clear for the ozone formation (human health, terrestrial ecosystems), acidification, fossil resource scarcity and water consumption indicators. Specifically, major effects are calculated for fossil resource scarcity (about 90% improvement with the highest recycling rate in Europe) and for ozone formation, with an improvement in the order of 30% and a negative effect in the order of 10%-15%. It is highlighted that for global warming potential, both the best and worst scenarios a significant improvement with respect to baseline is calculated, due to the

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fact that for this product, under the assumptions of the study, landfill presents a lower global warming potential than incineration.

Table 23. Influence of EoL treatments on AHPs value chain – Mini Pallets

Impact Category	Best case	Worst case
Global warming	-213%	76%
Ozone formation, Human health	-61%	24%
Ozone formation, Terrestrial ecosystems	-73%	30%
Terrestrial acidification	-21%	11%
Fossil resource scarcity	-633%	361%
Water consumption	-29%	17%

For the case of mini-pallets obtained from recycling AHPs products, the influence of different scenarios of EoL treatments, with specific reference to the recycling rate is evident and not-negligible. The most sensitive indicators are fossil resource scarcity and global warming, with percentages exceeding 200% in terms of achievable benefits from increasing the recycling rate and over 70% in terms of worsening the performance by decreasing the recycling rate. All the remaining indicators present improvements ranging from 30% to 75% and potential negative effects with a variation from 10% to 30% with respect to baseline.

1.2.7 RECAP OF MAIN FINDINGS

This section presents a recap of the main findings about the influence of national factors for the CIRCPACK value chains, already presented at single value chain level in the previous sections. It is noticed that such results are highly value-chain specific and should not be generalized to other products.

For a correct interpretation of the results, it should be highlighted that electricity mixes used as best case and worst case are selected based on the performance in the GWP impact category, thus, the sensitivity of this category to different electricity mixes is the most robust result, while different conclusions may be drawn if selecting scenarios based on different indicators.

As for the environmental influence of the national electricity mix, assuming that electricity is taken from the national grid, the following results are calculated:

- the influence of the electricity mix on each environmental indicator is different in amount, even though most of the indicator vary in similar ranges for each single value chain;
- negative and positive influence are unbalanced, due to the methodological approach selected;
- for most of the value chains, the highest achievable benefits from varying the electricity mix are in terms of global warming potential and terrestrial acidification; the achievable reduction from baseline can reach 70% for global warming potential and 80% for terrestrial acidification;

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- for most of the value chains, the highest potential negative impacts from varying the electricity mix are in terms of ozone formation (human health and ecosystem), reaching percentages of over 200%.

As far as the economic influence of electricity price on the OPEX cost for each value chain, it appears that the sensitivity of the OPEX is limited whenever biobased polymers are used as raw material, considering that they can have significant market prices. In the other cases, it is observed that electricity cost can be a significant contributor to the OPEX and, thus, variations to the electricity price may lead to more significant effects.

As for the environmental influence of the EoL route, the following results are calculated:

- the influence of the EoL on each environmental indicator is similar within each single value chain (excluding AHPs value chains);
- negative and positive influence are unbalanced, due to intrinsic properties of the scenarios analyzed;
- benefits from varying the EoL scenario range up to over 200% in terms of global warming potential. Significant benefits are also calculated for fossil resource scarcity for some value chains, due to the different values of recycling rates assumed;
- negative potential impacts from varying the EoL scenario on global warming potential may reach almost 70%, but are generally lower. Also from this perspective, fossil resource scarcity stands as sensible impact categories.

1.3 FOCUS ON TRANSPORT THRESHOLDS

At current stage of the project, the sustainability of values chains has been evaluated mostly independently from the transportation distances covered along the product value chain.

However, it is well-known that the influence of the impacts deriving from the transport phase may play a significant role in the environmental analysis of a product's life-cycle.

In order to address this problem from a general perspective, the suggested approach is the following:

- gap analysis between the innovative product and traditional product, in terms of GHG emissions, with correspondent EoL scenarios whenever possible;
- calculation of the maximum distances that can be travelled without exceeding the gap calculated, by different means of transportation (average size and large size truck, freight train, electric freight train) mostly used for European transport routes.

In the analysis above, the global warming potential has been selected as suitable indicators as it is the most powerful and well-established indicator from an environmental perspective. In addition, this indicator is among the most particularly relevant in the transport sector, which is associated with significant amount of greenhouse gases emissions not only in Europe, but also worldwide.

It is highlighted that this approach has the following limitations:

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- the maximum threshold obtained as result represents **the maximum additional distance that can be sustainably travelled in additional to the distance travelled in the traditional value chain**. Such relative approach can be overcome by setting a default distance travelled for the value chains.
- the possibility of combining different means of transportation across the stages of the life cycle is not taken into account, considering that the number of possible combinations is not accountable.

Moreover, the analysis is relevant in those cases in which the performance of CIRCPACK value chains expressed as GWP is better than the one of traditional value chains. It is however highlighted that while for this analysis this indicator is a proxy for environmental performance, CIRCPACK value chains can still be considered as positive innovations for many other parameters (e.g.: circularity index, resource depletion, etc.), as demonstrated in other phases of the project.

The input data necessary for the analysis are the GHG emissions factors for the operation phase of the analysis above. Table 24 below shows the global warming potential for 1 tkm of different means of transportation, calculated with the Recipe 2016 impact assessment method.

Table 24. Global Warming Potential of different means of transportation

Mean of Transportation	GWP [kgCO _{2e} /tkm]
Truck (16-32 ton), EURO6	0.166
Truck (>32 ton), EURO6	0.0876
Freight train (electricity driven)	0.0134
Freight ship (Ro-ro, 1,200 to 10,000 dwt)	0.0310

Thus, Table 25 illustrates, for the relevant CIRCPACK solutions, the performance gap between the innovative product and traditional product and the transport-distance proposals associated with this gap. All the values are expressed in km and are given as order of magnitude, in line with the level of detail of the overall analysis and assumptions.

For the value chains not included, the performance in terms of GWP for the innovative and traditional value chains is comparable.

Table 25. Differential threshold Distances for Different Means of Transportation [km]

Product	Truck 16-32 ton EURO6	Truck >32 ton EURO6	Freight train	Freight ship
Powder detergent box	4E+03	8E+03	5E+04	2E+04
Automotive components	1E+04	2E+04	1E+05	6E+04
AHPs – Secondary packaging	2E+03	3E+03	2E+04	1E+04
AHPs – Pamper box	1E+04	3E+04	2E+05	8E+04
AHPs – Mini pallets	7E+03	1E+04	8E+04	4E+04

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2 TECHNICAL AND NON-TECHNICAL REQUIREMENTS FOR REPLICATION

This chapter introduces technical and non-technical requirements needed for replication of CIRC-PACK value chains across EU. Requirements for replication are intended to highlight the aspects that can incisively drive the implementation of the value chain within a country. Considering the level of detail of the analysis, the outlined criteria are applicable to all the value chains.

2.1 TECHNICAL REQUIREMENTS

Technical requirements for replication concern, for example, availability of local virgin and secondary materials, presence of multiple industrial sectors, waste management facilities and their distribution on the territory.

Availability and relevance of local resources

CIRC-PACK value chains are univocally based on key products and flows. An easy availability of materials and substances necessary for their manufacturing is crucial to facilitate and generate the installation of suitable plants, as well as waste flows needed for the generation of secondary raw materials to feed the value chains are produced in sufficient amount within the area.

The availability and relevance of local resources is thus determinant to guarantee continuous and reliable supply to stakeholders involved in the manufacturing phases, while contributing to minimize costs (economic, environmental) sustained for duties, logistic and transport. Also, from of a social perspective, the involvement of local actors has positive effects, as it can contribute to improve the social acceptance of the innovative products, by creating local employment.

Waste collection and separation capacity

The capacity of collecting and sorting large amounts of waste is a driver for the implementation of successful and profitable value chains and symbioses. Such capacity derives from a combination of citizens' education to municipal waste management (or other wastes) and of the enforcement of efficient and user-friendly schemes for an adequate separate collection at municipal level. Proper collection and sorting has direct impact on quality and quantity of materials captures and on waste reprocessing capacity and indirect impact on the availability of local resources, according to the principles of circular economy and bioeconomy.

Waste reprocessing capacity

The technological capacity to reprocess multiple and large waste flows increases the potential of successful implementation of the value chains, allowing a greater availability of local resources (see previous requirement). Moreover, the presence of reprocessing plants is a proxy for the possibility of access –at local scale – to technologies and to technological background useful for the implementation of the desired value chains.

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The reprocessing capacity is also valued at macro-scale level, waste reprocessing capacity is closely related to recovery and recycling rates for plastic and for packaging, which works as a transparent indicator for the availability of local resources, in terms of secondary raw materials and the possibility of recovering packaging waste at end-of-life.

Functional clusterization of industries on territory

The location and level of aggregation of industrial areas on the territory influences the way and the possibility of implementing industrial synergies. For example, if industries are highly clustered within a local region i.e.: they are concentrated in industrial areas, easily accessible, exchanges between them can be implemented with limited effort. On the other hand, if industries are typically spread in different locations, which can also be isolated, interconnections may turn complex from a logistic and technical perspective, resulting in increased costs and environmental burdens.

2.2 NON-TECHNICAL REQUIREMENTS

Non-technical requirements for replication concern the regulatory, administrative and economic conditions necessary to allow an effective implementation of the value chains.

Existence of a market demand

A successful establishment of a value chain is triggered by the existence of a market demand for the end-products of the manufacturing process. Market demand is a crucial factor to positively activate and possibly sustain all the stages of each manufacturing chain.

Within CIRCPACK project, a market analysis for the exploitation of the main results is performed in WP7. The analysis identifies categories of end users/customers potentially interested in the products obtained: as an example, manufacturers of primary, secondary, and tertiary plastic packaging may create demand for fully bio-degradable multilayer solutions and plastic packaging. The quantitative estimation of such demand can influence the decision of replicating a value chain in a certain country rather than in other.

Support of governments to improve circular value chains: policy framework, financing and administrative burden

Opportunities and drivers promoted by governments may act as determinant facilitators for the implementation of circular economy strategies.

In recent years, several policy actions at EU level have been focusing on circular economy and associated business models. On 2 December 2015, the European Commission put forward a package to support the EU's transition to a circular economy. The EU Action Plan for the Circular Economy outlines a set of both general and material-specific actions.

The circular economy has also gained momentum in the policies of Members States, largely due to the political priority given to it by the EU in recent years. Some MS have developed dedicated circular economy strategies and roadmaps (France, Netherlands, Finland, etc.). A growing number of regions (Flanders, the Basque country, etc.) are now acting to develop a circular economy and they have been joined by a number of cities (Amsterdam, London, etc.). Some have adopted circular economy strategies, while others have introduced the

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circular economy in their sectoral policies (waste, economy, agriculture, bio-economy, construction etc.).

The main enablers that can be offered with the aim of supporting the creation and development of circular value chain within a country include:

- the **enforcement of a consistent national policy framework**, effectively addressing responsibilities across all the stages of the value chains, involving all the interested stakeholders, from the manufacturing phase to waste collection and management and to reprocessing activities;
- the **financial and economic aspects of a project** are naturally crucial elements for replication. A sound project's financing analysis should be based on the evaluation, inter alia, of the following elements: financial costs, financial risks, hidden and unforeseen costs, and financial solutions. The allocation of national funds can facilitate and unlock the implementation of value chains presenting economic criticalities. They can be offered in form of incentives, tax reductions, grant, etc. A positive financial influence from governments contribute to increase innovative products' price competitiveness against traditional products on the market;
- **minimization of bureaucracy requirements** to get access to the available instruments, including an adequate presence of offices, hiring of sufficient appointed staff, online platform for remote access to services.

Engagement of enterprises in promoting circular economy

In countries where enterprises and industries are traditionally engaged and interested in the creation of synergies and linkages, the realization of circular and innovative value chains can turn easier and more fruitful than under circumstances in which there is no interest for these strategies. In addition, a clear and concrete involvement of stakeholders in these mechanisms may encourage the development and implementation of actions of governments in the perspective of circular economy.

Customers' awareness about circular economy

Customers have been reported as strong drivers for greening activities and their demands have a strong influence on the decisions that companies take towards eco-design.

The level of awareness about circular economy principles among customers is important because it leads to the shifting of user buying intention towards environmentally friendly goods, determining the success of a value chain, which depends directly on the end-users demand, generated by their perception and satisfaction. If citizens are properly educated about environmental themes, such as green labelling, marketing and advertising, it is more likely that they purchase, consume products designed according to environmentally sustainable principles, even in those cases when they are not particularly competitive on the market. Moreover, it is also more likely that they are careful in implementing the suggested actions for proper end-of-life management.

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2.1 IMPORTANCE AND PRIORITY OF THE REQUIREMENTS

This section presents the results of an investigation, carried out among the partners of the project, to understand, based on the experience developed, the importance of each of the requirements above presented and their priority when aiming at the implementation of circular schemes.

Such outcome is useful to create robust indications about the most crucial factors enabling the replicability of the schemes proposed and implemented within the CIRCPACK project.

The form used for the investigation is included as ANNEX A.

On the basis of the information received through the investigation, it was considered effective to draw up a ranking of the ten requirements above presented, in order to identify and consequently clearly illustrate the main aspects to be considered for circular economy replicability. The classification was compiled focusing on the opinions assigned by the partners on importance and priority of technical and non-technical requirements.

Table 26, Table 27 and Table 28 show the defined ranking, where a low ranking value representing a high importance and priority for the requirement and a high ranking value representing a more limited importance and priority for the requirement.

In detail, Table 26 illustrates a general classification, considering both technical and non-technical requirements, whereas, Table 27 and Table 28 divide the two types of requirements, presenting two different more specific classifications.

Table 26: Requirements general ranking

Requirements	Ranking
Waste collection and separation capacity	1
Waste reprocessing capacity	2
Enforcement of a consistent national policy framework	3
Financial and economic aspects of a project	4
Existence of a market demand	5
Customers' awareness about circular economy and environmental	6
Minimization of bureaucracy requirements	7
Availability and relevance of local resources	8
Engagement of enterprises in promoting circular economy	9
Functional clusterization of industries on territory	10

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Table 27: Technical requirements ranking

Requirements Cluster	Requirements	Ranking
TECHNICAL REQUIREMENTS FOR REPLICABILITY	Waste collection and separation capacity	1
	Waste reprocessing capacity	2
	Availability and relevance of local resources	3
	Functional clusterization of industries on territory	4

Table 28: Non-Technical requirements ranking

Requirements Cluster	Requirements	Ranking
NON-TECHNICAL REQUIREMENTS FOR REPLICABILITY	Enforcement of a consistent national policy framework	1
	Financial and economic aspects of a project	2
	Existence of a market demand	3
	Customers' awareness about circular economy and environmental	4
	Minimization of bureaucracy requirements	5
	Engagement of enterprises in promoting circular economy	6

The following text illustrates the information obtained from the questionnaires, used to define the classification of requirements, in particular the general one. The two more specific classifications (technical and non-technical) have been carried out as a consequence of the general ranking.

As it can be seen from previous tables, it emerged that the majority of the interviewed partners considered the waste collection and separation capacity of high importance for the successful implementation of circular economy schemes in the plastic sector, also highlighting a high priority in comparison to other typical drivers. However, it was also pointed out that this aspect should be coupled with the capacity of treating not only large amounts of waste, but also a large variety of waste fractions, even though technical risks may unfortunately overwhelm the sorting efficiency and capacity. To compensate this latter aspect, a standard communication of the specific properties of each material should be pursued.

Moreover, consistent National and European policy frameworks result very important, in order to have a robust support focused on circular economy replicability, as well as financial and economic aspect. Considering this last point, the majority of interviewed partners stressed the importance of the introduction of tax incentives for the production of "circular" products (e.g. productions that follow the principles of eco-design).

According to the results of the investigation, both existence of market demand and customer's awareness about circular economy are considered two important aspects to replicate circular economy value chains. With respect to the issue of awareness, it was also pointed out the importance of the involvement of brand-owners, in order to achieve a more robust change also from an internal point of view of companies.

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Minimization of bureaucracy requirements is considered as a facilitator of replicability. Bureaucracy is often considered an important barrier for companies wishing to commit to the use of waste as a raw material.

The last three requirements of the general ranking are the availability and relevance of local sources, engagement of enterprises in promoting circular economy and functional clusterization of industries on territory.

Considering the availability and relevance of local sources, it emerged that often the supply of resources is carried out at global scale, on the global market, especially for companies for which availability and waste reprocessing are critical for high volumes and standards demanding manufacture (e.g. automotive plastic facility).

Moving on, the engagement of enterprises in promoting circular economy is considered important, but not necessarily crucial, despite the importance of the involvement of brand-owners is emerged as previously mentioned. However, a pool of enterprises that has the same challenge can help in changing the manufacturing ideas.

Finally, the functional clusterization of industries on territory is considered a driver, because many collaborations are already in progress, in particular for multinational enterprises. However, some partners also underline the importance of the opportunity to create collaborations between public and private stakeholders.

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3 IDENTIFICATION OF CASES FOR REPLICATION

This section presents the outcomes of a set of interviews carried out to find cases potentially suitable for the replication of CIRCPACK demo cases in Italy, Croatia, Germany and Spain as CIRCPACK representative Countries and, in addition, Portugal.

The interviews have been collected by ICLEI, by oral interviews structured on the basis of a questionnaire tailored for the purpose. Both the questionnaire and the transcripts of the interviews are attached as ANNEXES (B-G).

The questionnaire is structured in order to investigate the performance of each city in qualitative terms with respect to each replicability criteria and each CIRCPACK demo case scheme. Specifically, for each replicability criteria, a qualitative evaluation of performance is assessed separately for each demo case scheme. As a second step of the investigation, potential sectors and sets of industries in which the demo cases can be implemented as value chains are identified, based on the information available to the city's representative, whenever available.

The sub-sections below synthetically illustrate the main results of the interviews, especially covering a recap of the overall status of replicability for the value chains, as well main actors involved and particular initiative or highlights of interest.

3.1 TURIN (ITALY)

The city of Turin offers interesting and variegated opportunities and drivers for the development of circular value chains in plastic packaging section (e.g.: planned introduction of a rewards scheme based on the amount of waste generated; planned introduction of a certification scheme for sustainable and eco-friendly management of all events; engagement in H2020 projects on the theme).

In addition, Turin presents an established waste management system for both plastic waste and organic waste (including biodegradable and compostable plastic). In the specific case of organic waste, the plant of ACEA company, which is used by all organic waste management service providers in the north-western part of the Piedmont Region, carries out aerobic and anaerobic treatment of waste, to produce biogas and high quality compost for agricultural use. The company's integrated circular economy approach has attracted international attention and provided a foundation for partnerships with research institutions.

The results of the interview show that for all the schemes (i.e.: demo cases) investigated, there are not critical technical or non-technical bottlenecks, except for a general lack of financial support.

3.2 ZAGREB (CROATIA)

The city of Zagreb presents some opportunities for the replication of circular value chains for plastic packaging products, however, there is still space for improvement of technical and non-technical background to facilitate the implementation of such systems.

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The replication of DC-A and DC-B is considered as more suitable for the case private companies. For the City of Zagreb itself, it might be applicable the DC-C Enhanced Sorting and recycling / creating an effective after-use plastics economy (see diagram below).

According to the additional information provided during the interview for the case of Zagreb, it is very important to educate the population at all levels and in multiple sectors. In order to achieve the highest possible degree of separation of waste and to increase sorted waste quality for further processing, additional efforts need to be made to create clean environmental awareness. Despite the improvement in the last few years, only when the necessary municipal infrastructure will be finished, a close waste management system will be available. At that point, City of Zagreb will be able to give greater importance to the circular economy as well. The construction of municipal infrastructure will establish the best available technology for waste treatment and the results of the treatment will be better and the City of Zagreb will fulfill its obligations for separate waste collection. In parallel, work should be done to strengthen the private sector, which, in addition to urban municipal infrastructure, will be an additional element in waste treatment, such as using a new formulation of secondary raw materials generated in a recycling plant.

The main stakeholders in the process of implementing circular value chains would be the City of Zagreb and Holding, which would coordinate activities to establish a better quality waste management system. With them, a very important part would be related to information and education. And the third part of the stakeholders are those who would take this new raw material and continue to use it in production

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DC-C REPLICABILITY IN ZAGREB

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3.3 FREIBURG (GERMANY)

The city of Freiburg demonstrates solid basis for the replication of circular value chains for plastic packaging products. It achieves a fair or high level across the requirements, except for the case of financial support from the government, for which potential bottlenecks may arise. In general terms, it has good potentialities especially in terms of customer awareness, reflected also in high market demand of sustainable products by the end-users. Overall, the replication of value chains falling under the scheme of DC-A seems the most promising, but the status is quite balanced also for the other cases.

The “Abfallwirtschaft Freiburg” (ASF), in majority owned by the City of Freiburg, has the mandate to collect all kinds of waste. Industrial waste is up for competition, but depending on the company/facility, ASF covers all waste fractions here as well. For organic waste, all waste is being processed by city-owned facility RETERRA, giving outputs compost and biomethane. In the entire Germany, reprocessing of lightweight packaging is subject to the so-called “dual system” (introduced in 1990ies) according to which packaged product fees integrated in the end price of the product are collected and re-distributed – at national level - across the different companies of the system, depending on the territory they cover. Quality and quantity of packaging waste treated is hence not clear as the information is not shared by the dual system.

The City of Freiburg has Waste Management Concept from 2015 that highlights the city's own ambition, setting targets and perspectives for the future. The city is currently working on new concept that will introduce new plans, specifically with regard to boosting the circular economy. The “Abfallsatzung” (Engl. Waste Charter) is a legal document for the local level in Germany which determines waste flows, quantities, treatment options, fees etc. and is the most important legal instrument in waste management.

What the city can currently advocate for is the reduction- and separation of waste. Freiburg is known in Germany for having many citizens conscious to the causal relationships between resource consumption and environmental pressures and hence are deemed open to buying recycled packaging or biodegradable plastic in general.

3.4 SEVILLA (SPAIN)

The city of Sevilla presents good opportunities for the replication of circular value chains for plastic packaging products. Indeed, it demonstrates a fair level of development of most of the technical requirements identified for a positive replication. As for non-technical requirements, a more detailed analysis and study of circular economy processes within the city would likely lead to a more favorable background and would increase awareness among involved actors.

In this context, DC-C “Enhanced sorting and recycling” – for which a supporting action is given within the policy framework – is identified as the most suitable for replication (see diagram below), especially with reference to plastic waste deriving from the food chain (e.g.: supermarkets, distributors, etc.) for the manufacturing of tetra pack packaging products..

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DC-C REPLICABILITY IN SEVILLA

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3.5 KARTAL (TURKEY)

The city of Kartal presents still significant improvement to achieve in order to boost the scheme of circular economy, from both a technical and non-technical perspective. However, the finding of the interview suggest that DC-A and DC-B are those presenting higher replicability potential (see also diagram below).

Vatan Plastik and Cesur Packagingj are the main plastic packaging material manufacturers in Kartal. They have their own plastic sorting plant. In details, Vatan Plastic is producing greenhouse films, stretch film, shrink film, stretch hood, plasticisers, fluid plastics, additives and refuse sacks. The firm states that there are 2 recycling plants and Polyethylene (PE) and Polypropylene (PP) recycling operations are made in the facilities, that the obtained granules have certificate from Turkish Standards Institute, and that they purchase PE and PP Production / Package wastes from the companies. Cesur Packaging states that production wastes such as PP, LDPE are recovered in the in-house recycling facility but are never used in their own production but are sold to masterbatch producers, injectioners and producers of low-quality yarn for different usage areas, gaining economically with the process. Composite packaging is not favourable to collect because of high recycling cost, so the collecting is not made with packaging waste. The main NGOs related to plastic industry in Turkey are PAGDER (Plastic Industrialists Association), PLASFED (Plastic Industrialists Federation), ASD (Packaging Waste Industrialists Association), PAGEV (Turkish Plastics Industry Foundation). ÇEVKO (Environmental Protection and Packaging Waste Recovery and Recycling Trust), TÜKÇEV (Turkey Consumer and Environmental Education Foundation), AGED (Waste Paper and Recyclers Association) are the authorized bodies in managing, coordinating, supporting packaging waste collection, sorting, education, by the Ministry of Environment and Urbanisation mentioned in the Packaging Wastes Regulation.

Overall, in Turkey, the licensed sorting plant owners have problems selling the collected material to manufacturers. The price and request of the manufacturers do not absorb the collecting, sorting and storage costs of the enterprises, thus making the local circular value chain difficult to establish, considering also inputs from imported material is in the market.

From a regulatory perspective, the Packaging Waste Regulation and Zero Waste Regulation control the production, collection, sorting and recycling of packaging materials, forcing municipalities to organize the regular collection and reporting of the waste management steps with the support of licensed firms and authorized bodies, responding to the material and information requests of local people, to ensure collection of regulated target rates.

According to public survey carried out online by 269 Kartal residents and 790 Turkish people in the framework of CIRC-PACK project; Turkish respondents are highly willing to buy low-environmental impact products and they also are ambitious to do it even if it implies a higher price; however, at the moment biobased material is used in promotional products such as sprouting pencil, block note, greeting card with seed ball etc. The rate of collecting packaging waste increases day by day. The plastic waste contamination in drinking water PET bottles, in the oceans and seas is highlighted by environmental NGOs on media and people is getting more attentive in buying recyclable packaging and sorting plastic wastes in collecting bins.

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DEMO CASE A “Plastics from renewable resources”

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3.6 PORTO (PORTUGAL)

The city of Porto shows good opportunities for the replication of circular value chains for plastic packaging products. In particular, it seems to have a fertile ground especially for the implementation of circular schemes falling under DC-B and DC-C, whereas for DC-A a low waste treatment capacity, in terms of collection and reprocessing, may hamper the development. Differently from the other cities, it shows high level of support from policy initiatives that cover all the demo cases.

Overall, as in Portugal, there is growing interest for secondary materials and also large companies are having the concern of using mainly recycled materials. On the other side, the interest in manufacturing bio-based products is now beginning, with smaller companies and universities playing a major role in the development and diffusion of these kind of products. From the demand side, the final customers do have an interest in buying sustainable products as a result of a growing awareness, however, cost affects the choice in the moment of purchase. Considering that the recycling rates have been growing in Porto as never before, it is recognized as essential to continuously invest in citizens, giving them the necessary information and raising their awareness, because they are final customers and make the final decisions, and therefore the economy will not be circular without their support.

Finally, the Circular Economy is a key theme in the Municipal Environment Strategy in which high attention has been put, as well as a substantial part of our effort with very concrete actions. Initiatives of companies to promote circular economy already exist in the sectors of electric and electronic equipment (e.g.: Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment Recovery Centers), dissemination of best practices (Cidade+), etc.

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4 CONCLUSIONS

The aim of this deliverable is the identification of a roadmap for replicability of new plastic packaging value chains.

Based on a high-level evaluation of national **material indicators, R&D indicators, economic indicators and social indicators**, a selection of Countries presenting **good performance in terms of status of advancement of circular economy**, implying a good potential for the replicability of CIRCPACK innovations is identified. As a quantitative assessment, the environmental influence of **electricity mix** and **end-of-life** route as national based factors is investigated for each value chain, highlighting how the results largely vary from one product to another as well as from one impact indicator to another. In general terms, it is observed that the highest achievable benefits from varying the electricity mix are in terms of global warming potential and terrestrial acidification. On the other hand, benefits from varying the EoL scenario range up to over 200% in terms of global warming potential, but significant benefits are also calculated for fossil resource scarcity for some value chains. Moreover, the economic influence of **electricity price** on the OPEX cost for each value chain is analysed: it results that a low cost of electricity may lead to significant savings especially for the value chains not relying on biopolymers, which can constitute the highest share of the OPEX.

Moreover, the **distance thresholds to ensure sustainability** of the innovative value chains with respect to traditional practice are estimated for different means of transportation. For the value chains assessed, differential thresholds distances range from 10^3 km (trucks) to a maximum of 10^5 km (freight train).

With the aim of guiding the replicability, a selection of technical and non-technical criteria that should be assessed is retrieved. These are:

- availability and relevance of local resources;
- waste collection and separation capacity;
- waste reprocessing capacity;
- functional clusterization of industries on territory;
- existence of a market demand;
- support of governments to improve circular value chains: policy framework, financing and administrative burden;
- engagement of enterprises in promoting circular economy;
- customers' awareness about circular economy and environmental.

Finally, based on the aforementioned replicability requirements, **5 cities potentially suitable for the replication of circular value chains in the plastic packaging sector**, based on CIRCPACK demo cases are presented, highlighting their opportunities and potential bottlenecks for the implementation of circular schemes.

To conclude, in general terms, the variegated analyses and evaluations performed within this work offer a wide overview on the aspects to take into consideration to structure a **realistic roadmap for replicability**. These findings have also led to the identification of real cases, covering countries and cities, towards which the replication of circular economy in the plastic packaging value chains may be addressed.

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6 ANNEXES

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6.1 ANNEX A – FORM FOR ASSESSMENT OF REPLICABILITY CRITERIA

INSTRUCTIONS FOR COMPILATION							
Detailed description of the meaning of replicability requirements is provided in the word file "D6.5_replicability requirements".							
For each requirement, you are kindly asked to provide the following answers:							
- IMPORTANCE : please mark the desired importance rate considering the following legend: HIGH : the requirement is crucial for the replicability and it enables any circular scheme in plastic packaging value chains; MEDIUM : the requirement is a facilitator and accelerator for replicability; LOW : the requirement plays only a marginal role for a successful replicability							
- PRIORITY : please rate the priority of each requirement. Use number 1 for the requirement with highest priority and then proceed numbering in descending order of priority							
- DETAILS : please justify answers given for the specific requirement, especially based on the experience and knowledge you developed in CIRCPACK project							
Each cell should be filled.							
			IMPORTANCE			PRIORITY	DETAILS
			high	medium	low		
TECHNICAL REQUIREMENTS FOR REPLICABILITY	Availability and relevance of local resources						
	Waste collection and separation capacity						
	Waste reprocessing capacity						
	Functional clusterization of industries on territory						
NON TECHNICAL REQUIREMENTS FOR REPLICABILITY	Existence of a market demand						
	Support of governments to improve circular value chains: policy framework, financing and administrative burden	enforcement of a consistent national policy framework					
		financial and economic aspects of a project					
		minimization of bureaucracy requirements					
	Engagement of enterprises in promoting circular economy						
Customers' awareness about circular economy and environmental							

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6.2 ANNEX B – SUPPORT QUESTIONNAIRE FOR INTERVIEW

CIRC-PACK (Towards circular economy in the plastic packaging value chain) aimed to develop a more sustainable, efficient, and competitive, less fossil fuel dependent, integrated and interconnected plastic value chain.

To this end, the project worked on three different topical issues in the form of Demo Cases:

- A. **Demo Case A: Plastics from renewable sources** / decoupling the chain from fossil feedstock
 - o Development of new bio-based and biodegradable bioplastics formulations
 - o Replaces the chemical Butanediol, made from fossil fuels, with Bio-Butanediol
 - o Bio-butanediol is produced from sugars derived from starches
 - o Bio-butanediol is produced at a dedicated plant

- B. **Demo Case B: Eco-friendly packaging design** / introducing innovative formats and reducing the negative environmental impact of plastic packaging
 - o eco-friendly packaging designs, specially adapted for bio-based materials.
 - o Industry partners produce multilayer and multi-material packaging that can be easily recycled.
 - o Bio-plastic component can either be degradable in nature; or
 - o be separated into separate monomaterials in a paper recycling process

- C. **Demo Case C: Enhanced Sorting and recycling** / creating an effective after-use plastics economy
 - o improves current recycling facilities to increase the production yield
 - o Adaptation of current technologies for recycling Polythene bags to recycle bio-based bags
 - o New methodology for recycling **post-industrial** wastes (scrap and failure parts) in automotive parts
 - o New formula using the secondary raw materials (cellulose, plastic) generated in a recycling plant for Absorbent Hygiene Products (AHP) waste
 - o New methodology has proven that it is possible to reduce the difference between different materials during the extrusion phase.

The three demo cases are intertwined, but also work as stand-alone solutions to improve the sustainability of the plastic value chain.

Below, a selection of requirements for replicability of CIRCPACK value chains and demo cases is proposed, covering technical and non-technical factors.

Each city should answer a brief set of questions for each requirement. The purpose of such questions is to guide each city to a self-evaluation of suitability to replicate one or more demo-case schemes with respect to the local context.

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Technical Requirements

Technical requirements for replication concern, for example, availability of local virgin and secondary materials, presence of multiple industrial sectors, waste management facilities and their distribution on the territory.

Availability and relevance of local resources

CIRC-PACK value chains are univocally based on key products and flows. An easy availability of materials and substances necessary for their manufacturing is crucial to facilitate and generate the installation of suitable plants, as well as waste flows needed for the generation of secondary raw materials to feed the value chains are produced in sufficient amount within the area.

The availability and relevance of local resources is thus determinant to guarantee continuous and reliable supply to stakeholders involved in the manufacturing phases, while contributing to minimize costs (economic, environmental) sustained for duties, logistic and transport. Also, from of a social perspective, the involvement of local actors has positive effects, as it can contribute to improve the social acceptance of the innovative products, by creating local employment.

- **How would you describe the status-quo of your geographical context with respect to this requirement?**
.....
- **Therefore, how would you rate the potential of replicability of CIRCPACK demo cases?**

Availability and relevance of local resources			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low availability of renewable feedstock	Fair availability of renewable feedstock	High availability of renewable feedstock
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	Low availability of local resources	Fair availability of local resources	High availability of local resources
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	Low availability of local resources	Fair availability of local resources	High availability of local resources
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Waste collection and separation capacity

The capacity of collecting and sorting large amounts of waste is a driver for the implementation of successful and profitable value chains and symbioses. Such capacity derives from a combination of citizens' education to municipal waste management (or other wastes) and of the enforcement of efficient schemes for an adequate separate collection at municipal level. Proper collection and sorting have direct impact on waste reprocessing capacity and indirect impact on the availability of local resources.

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Waste collection and separation capacity			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants for bio-based plastics	Fair availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants for bio-based plastics	High availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants for bio-based plastics
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	Low availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants	Fair availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants	High availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	Low availability of advanced separate collection schemes and sorting plants	Fair availability of advanced separate collection schemes and sorting plants	High availability of advanced separate collection schemes and sorting plants
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Waste reprocessing capacity

The technological capacity to reprocess multiple and large waste flows increases the potential of successful implementation of the value chains, allowing a greater availability of local resources (see previous requirement). Moreover, the presence of reprocessing plants is a proxy for the possibility of access –at local scale – to technologies and to technological background useful for the implementation of the desired value chains.

The reprocessing capacity is also valued at macro-scale level, waste reprocessing capacity is closely related to recovery and recycling rates for plastic and for packaging, which works as a transparent indicator for the availability of local resources, in terms of secondary raw materials and the possibility of recovering packaging waste at end-of-life.

Waste reprocessing capacity			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low availability of treatment plants for bio-based plastics waste	Fair availability of treatment plants for bio-based plastics waste	High availability of treatment plants for bio-based plastics waste
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	Low availability of treatment plants for plastics waste	Fair availability of treatment plants for plastics waste	High availability of treatment plants for plastics waste
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	Low availability of advanced treatment plants for plastics waste	Fair availability of advanced treatment plants for plastics waste	High availability of advanced treatment plants for plastics waste
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Functional clusterization of industries on territory

The location and level of aggregation of industrial areas on the territory influences the way and the possibility of implementing industrial synergies. For example, if industries are highly

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clustered within a local region i.e.: they are concentrated in industrial areas, easily accessible, exchanges between them can be implemented with limited effort. On the other hand, if industries are typically spread in different locations, which can also be isolated, interconnections may turn complex from a logistic and technical perspective, resulting in increased costs and environmental burdens.

Functional clusterization of industries on territory			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Segmented clusterization: (industries are not properly interconnected)	Fair clusterization	High clusterization: (industries are efficiently interconnected)
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"			

Non-technical requirements

Non-technical requirements for replication concern the regulatory, administrative and economic conditions necessary to allow an effective implementation of the value chains.

Existence of a market demand

A successful establishment of a value chain is triggered by the existence of a market demand for the end-products of the manufacturing process. Market demand is a crucial factor to positively activate and possibly sustain all the stages of each manufacturing chain. Within CIRCPACK project, a market analysis for the exploitation of the main results is performed. The analysis identifies categories of end users/customers potentially interested in the products obtained: as an example, manufacturers of primary, secondary, and tertiary plastic packaging may create demand for fully bio-degradable multilayer solutions and plastic packaging. The quantitative estimation of such demand can influence the decision of replicating a value chain in a certain country rather than in other.

Existence of a market demand			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low end-users demand of bio-based products	Fair end-users demand of bio-based products	High end-users demand of bio-based products
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	Low end-users demand of recoverable products	Fair end-users demand of recoverable products	High end-users demand of recoverable products
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	Low manufacturers demand of secondary raw materials	Fair manufacturers demand of secondary raw materials	High manufacturers demand of secondary raw materials
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

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Support of governments to improve circular value chains: policy framework, financing and administrative burden

Opportunities and drivers promoted by governments may act as determinant facilitators for the implementation of circular economy strategies.

In recent years, several policy actions at EU level have been focusing on circular economy and associated business models. On 2 December 2015, the European Commission put forward a package to support the EU's transition to a circular economy. The EU Action Plan for the Circular Economy outlines a set of both general and material-specific actions.

The circular economy has also gained momentum in the policies of Members States, largely due to the political priority given to it by the EU in recent years. Some MS have developed dedicated circular economy strategies and roadmaps (France, Netherlands, Finland, etc.). A growing number of regions (Flanders, the Basque country, etc.) are now acting to develop a circular economy and they have been joined by a number of cities (Amsterdam, London, etc.). Some have adopted circular economy strategies, while others have introduced the circular economy in their sectoral policies (waste, economy, agriculture, bio-economy, construction etc.).

The main enablers that can be offered with the aim of supporting the creation and development of circular value chain within a country include:

- the **enforcement of a consistent national policy framework**, effectively addressing responsibilities across all the stages of the value chains, involving all the interested stakeholders, from the manufacturing phase to waste collection and management and to reprocessing activities;
- the **financial and economic aspects of a project** are naturally crucial elements for replication. A sound project's financing analysis should be based on the evaluation, inter alia, of the following elements: financial costs, financial risks, hidden and unforeseen costs, and financial solutions. The allocation of national funds can facilitate and unlock the implementation of value chains presenting economic criticalities. They can be offered in form of incentives, tax reductions, grant, etc. A positive financial influence from governments contribute to increase innovative products' price competitiveness against traditional products on the market;
- **minimization of bureaucracy requirements** to get access to the available instruments, including an adequate presence of offices, hiring of sufficient appointed staff, online platform for remote access to services.

Support of governments to improve circular value chains			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Unfavourable policy context	Fair policy context	Encouraging policy context
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Lack of financial support	Availability of financial support	Availability of consistent financial support
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	Complex and long bureaucracy requirements	Standard bureaucracy requirements	Easy-to-manage bureaucracy requirements
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Unfavourable policy context	Fair policy context	Encouraging policy context
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	Lack of financial support	Availability of financial support	Availability of consistent financial support
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Complex and long bureaucracy requirements	Standard bureaucracy requirements	Easy-to-manage bureaucracy requirements
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Engagement of enterprises in promoting circular economy

In countries where enterprises and industries are traditionally engaged and interested in the creation of synergies and linkages, the realization of circular and innovative value chains can turn easier and more fruitful than under circumstances in which there is no interest for these strategies. In addition, a clear and concrete involvement of stakeholders in these mechanisms may encourage the development and implementation of actions of governments in the perspective of circular economy.

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Engagement of enterprises in promoting circular economy			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low or none enterprises' effective commitment in circular economy implementation	Moderate enterprises' effective commitment in circular economy implementation	Notable enterprises' effective commitment in circular economy implementation
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"			
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"			
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Customers' awareness about circular economy and environmental

Customers have been reported as strong drivers for greening activities and their demands have a strong influence on the decisions that companies take towards eco-design. The level of awareness about circular economy principles among customers is important because it leads to the shifting of user buying intention towards environmentally friendly goods, determining the success of a value chain, which depends directly on the end-users demand, generated by their perception and satisfaction. If citizens are properly educated about environmental themes, such as green labelling, marketing and advertising, it is more likely that they purchase, consume products designed according to environmentally sustainable principles, even in those cases when they are not particularly competitive on the market. Moreover, it is also more likely that they are careful in implementing the suggested actions for proper end-of-life management.

Perceived engagement of enterprises in promoting circular economy			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low or none end-users' awareness about environmentally responsible purchases	Moderate end-users' awareness about environmentally responsible purchases	Notable end-users' awareness about environmentally responsible purchases
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"			
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"			
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

- **Considering the replicability self-assessment for all the requirements, overall, which demo case would you consider to be replicable in your local area?** (more than one answer can be provided)
 - DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"
 - DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"
 - DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"

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- **For the demo case(s) you considered as replicable, could you suggest one or more specific value chains (among those covered by the project, or similar) suitable to be implemented in the area of your city?**

.....

- **Finally, which local actors would you identify to represent relevant roles in the possible implementation of such circular value chain(s)?**

.....

Please fill the schemes proposed for the demo-cases you assessed as suitable for replicability by including local actors you would consider suitable to be integrated in a circular plastic packaging value chain

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DEMO CASE A “Plastics from renewable resources”

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DEMO CASE B “Eco-friendly packaging design”

Material manufacturers	Core business/value chain
.....
.....
.....
.....

Manufacturers	Core business/value chain
.....
.....
.....
.....

Polymerization and Bio-polymerization

Packaging Manufacturing

Multidisciplinary supporting bodies (research centres, organizations, etc.)

Entities, organizations:

-
-
-
-

Use

Companies, end users categories	Core business/value chain
.....
.....
.....
.....

Collection, sorting and recycling

Waste management companies	Core business/value chain
.....
.....
.....
.....

◀ **DEMO CASE C “Enhanced sorting and recycling”**

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6.3 ANNEX C – TURIN INTERVIEW

Representative of Environment Directorate, City of Torino

Technical Requirements

Availability and relevance of local resources

CIRC-PACK value chains are univocally based on key products and flows. An easy availability of materials and substances necessary for their manufacturing is crucial to facilitate and generate the installation of suitable plants, as well as waste flows needed for the generation of secondary raw materials to feed the value chains are produced in sufficient amount within the country. The availability and relevance of local resources is thus determinant to guarantee continuous and reliable supply to stakeholders involved in the manufacturing phases, while contributing to minimize costs (economic, environmental) sustained for duties, logistic and transport. Also from of a social perspective, the involvement of local actors has positive effects, as it can contribute to improve the social acceptance of the innovative products, by creating local employment.

Answer Summary:

The waste recycling rate in the City of Torino has risen steadily, with rapid improvements between 1995 and 2007 (2.9% to 36.9% respectively), reaching a plateau of around 40% from 2007 to 2016 and increasing more significantly again in the following years (42.7% in 2016, 44.7% in 2017 and 46% in 2018). From January to June 2019 a total of approximately 170,000 tons of plastic were collected in the City of Torino. In the same timeframe 25,407 tons of organic waste and 14,305 tons of glass were collected in the city (see Table 1 for further categories of waste). Approximately 116,568 tons of unsorted waste were processed during the six-month period.

The waste management department of Torino does not hold the remit for overseeing the management of sorting and processing plants. Another administrative body – a type of consortium that brings together the various municipalities in the area – called ATOR¹ is in charge this, covering the province of Torino and a small number of adjacent administrative areas. This division of responsibilities limits the City of Torino's ability to carry out improvements to activities related to sorting and processing waste. Further, the department consequently does not hold data on recycling rates nor does it have information on how waste resources are treated and integrated into value chains.

¹ <http://www.atorifiutitorinese.it/cms/> (Accessed on 24.02.2020)

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Availability and relevance of local resources*			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low availability of renewable feedstock	Fair availability of renewable feedstock	High availability of renewable feedstock
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	Low availability of local resources	Fair availability of local resources	High availability of local resources
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	x
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	Low availability of local resources	Fair availability of local resources	High availability of local resources
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>

* It is important to note that "availability" refers to volumes of raw materials disposed. As sorting and processing is coordinated at national level, access to these resources is limited to select private sector companies who are members of a CONAI consortium.

Type of Waste collected between January & June 2019	Amount of Waste (kg)	Company	Prov.	City	CONAI
					yes/no
Paper and cardboard	25.446,900	CMT	TO	PIANEZZA	YES
		CMT	TO	LA LOGGIA	YES
		CARTAMACERO	TO	TORINO	YES
		CARTAMACERO	TO	LEINI'	YES
		DS SMITH	TO	TORINO	NO
		DS SMITH	TO	TORINO	YES
		BENASSI	TO	GRUGLIASCO	NO
		BENASSI	TO	GRUGLIASCO	YES
		ECOPIEMONTE	TO	ORBASSANO	YES
		ECOPIEMONTE	TO	SAN MAURO	YES
Glass	14.304,790	ECOGLOSS SRL	SV	DEGO	YES
		EUROVETRO	VA	ORIGGIO	NO
Plastic	7.167,890	CMT	TO	LA LOGGIA	YES
		ECOPIEMONTE	TO	ORBASSANO	YES
		AMIAT SPA	TO	COLLEGNO	YES
		DEMAP	TO	BEINASCO	NO
		RICO SUD	SA	BATTIPAGLIA	NO
		BENASSI	TO	GRUGLIASCO	NO
Iron/steel	832,730	EMMEDI	TO	CASELLE TOR.	NO
		CRS	TO	SETTIMO T.SE	NO
Organic	25.407,040	AMIAT	TO	BORGARO T.SE	NO
		ACEA	TO	PINEROLO	NO
		ECOPROGETTO TORTONA	AL	TORTONA	NO
Wood	8.836,710	WOOD RECYCLING	TO	GRUGLIASCO	YES
		ECOLEGNO AIRASCA	TO	AIRASCA	YES
		SAIB	PC	CAORSO	YES
		IL TRUCIOLO	CO	ALBAVILLA	YES
Grass / twigs	606,920	AREA LEGNO GERMAGNANO	TO	TORINO	NO
Textiles	725,450	LAVORO E SOLIDARIETA'	TO	VEROLENGO	NO
From open air markets (boxes, plastic and wood)	1.478,890	AMIAT SPA	TO	COLLEGNO	NO
Very big items	2.561,340	AMIAT SPA	TO	COLLEGNO	NO
Electrical cables/battery charging	1.263,015	AMIAT TBD	TO	VOLPIANO	NO
		CONSORZI ADERENTI			NO
Mineral oil	16,055	SEPI AMBIENTE	TO	SETTIMO T.SE	NO

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Vegetables oil	17,940	SEPI AMBIENTE	TO	SETTIMO T.SE	NO
		MEANI	MI	BOLLATE	NO
Print toner	23,362	LA NUOVA COOPERATIVA	TO	TORINO	NO
Batteries	17,877	TRANSISTOR	TO	TORINO	NO
Drugs/medicaments	31,675	AREA RUP	TO	TORINO	NO
Accumulators	32,450	SEPI AMBIENTE	TO	SETTIMO T.SE	NO
		TREDECO	TO	SETTIMO T.SE	NO
Tires/gas cylinders	183,147	various			
Unsorted	116.567,960	CIDIU SPA	TO	PIANEZZA	NO
		ACEA AMBIENTE	TO	PINEROLO	NO
		ASRAB	BI	CAVAGLIA'	NO
		TRM	TO	TORINO	NO
Waste from household repairs	1.932,400	EDILCAVE TORINO	TO	TORINO	NO
		ICOS ECOLOGIA	TO	TORINO	NO
		REI	TO	COLLEGNO	NO
From Road Cleaning Activities	2.420,550	IREN AMBIENTE	PC	PIACENZA	NO
		LA NUOVA TERRA	MB	LENTATE	NO

Table 1. Type of Waste Collected in Administrative Area between January & June 2019 [Source: City of Torino]

Waste collection and separation capacity

The capacity of collecting and sorting large amounts of waste is a driver for the implementation of successful and profitable value chains and symbioses. Such capacity derives from a combination of citizens' education to municipal waste management (or other wastes) and of the enforcement of efficient schemes for an adequate separate collection at municipal level. Proper collection and sorting have direct impact on waste reprocessing capacity and indirect impact on the availability of local resources.

Answer Summary

The waste management department of Torino is member of a consortium that was established by the Piedmont Region in the 2000s now known as "Area 18". In the context of this consortium the department is responsible for overseeing waste collection (incl. household and special waste) in all territories of the municipality. Waste collection is contracted to the waste management service provider AMIAT SpA², which is in charge of the entire waste collection system and is monitored by the city's waste management department. Figure 1 identifies key waste collection infrastructure in the City of Torino.

Waste collection in the City of Torino currently includes pick-up points in building courtyards for smaller bins and collection points for medium-to-large bins. The administration aims to expand door-to-door collection of waste across the entire administered area in 2021, with more bins for various waste types set up in building courtyards, where spatially possible.

² <http://www.amiat.it/cms/en/> (Accessed on 21.02.2020)

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Waste collection and separation capacity			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants for bio-based plastics	Fair availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants for bio-based plastics	High availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants for bio-based plastics
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	Low availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants	Fair availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants	High availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	Low availability of advanced separate collection schemes and sorting plants	Fair availability of advanced separate collection schemes and sorting plants	High availability of advanced separate collection schemes and sorting plants
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>

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Figure 1: Overview of metropolitan collection and sweeping services provided by AMIAT SpA [in 2018]
 Source: http://www.amiat.it/cms/phocadownload/analisi%20ambientali%202018_sito%20gorini%20germagnano%20e%20raccolta%20territorio%20torino.pdf [Accessed on 23.02.2020]

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Waste reprocessing capacity

The technological capacity to reprocess multiple and large waste flows increases the potential of successful implementation of the value chains, allowing a greater availability of local resources (see previous requirement). Moreover, the presence of reprocessing plants is a proxy for the possibility of access –at local scale – to technologies and to technological background useful for the implementation of the desired value chains.

The reprocessing capacity is also valued at macro-scale level, waste reprocessing capacity is closely related to recovery and recycling rates for plastic and for packaging, which works as a transparent indicator for the availability of local resources, in terms of secondary raw materials and the possibility of recovering packaging waste at end-of-life.

Answer Summary

Plastic waste in the City of Torino is collected by the company AMIAT SpA and transported to a plant, where operators sort the resource to meet regionally / nationally defined quality thresholds. The raw plastic is then transported in bulk to the CSS Selection Center DEMAP (operated by a CONAI COREPLA³ consortium member) located in Beinasco on the outskirts of the city.

Organic waste is not managed by a CONAI consortium. In the City of Torino it is collected and brought to intermediary collection points by the company AMIAT SpA from where it is then transported in larger volume trucks to the plant of the company Acea Pinerolese Industriale SpA⁴ in Pinerolo, located approximately 30km from of Torino's urban center. The plant of ACEA, which is used by all organic waste management service providers in the north-western part of the Piedmont Region, carries out aerobic and anaerobic treatment of waste. Biogas produced by the treatment plant supplies district heating to part of the city of Pinerolo. Further, the plant produces quality compost, which is sold to farmers and gardeners. The company's integrated circular economy approach has attracted international attention⁵ and provided a foundation for partnerships with research institutions⁶.

³ www.corepla.it (Accessed on 21.02.2020)

⁴ <https://www.aceapinerolese.it/> (Accessed on 21.02.2020)

⁵ <https://www.aceapinerolese.it/la-multiutility-di-aalborg-quarta-citta-della-danimarca-in-visita-in-acea-pinerolese-per-conoscere-il-servizio-idrico-integrato/> (Accessed on 21.02.2020)

⁶ <https://www.aceapinerolese.it/accordo-tra-politecnico-di-torino-e-aceapinerolese-industriale-innovazione-ricerca-formazione-e-progetti-in-tema-di-bioenergie-chimica-verde-ed-economia-circolare/> (Accessed on 21.02.2020)

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Waste reprocessing capacity			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low availability of treatment plants for bio-based plastics waste	Fair availability of treatment plants for bio-based plastics waste	High availability of treatment plants for bio-based plastics waste
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	Low availability of treatment plants for plastics waste	Fair availability of treatment plants for plastics waste	High availability of treatment plants for plastics waste
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	Low availability of advanced treatment plants for plastics waste	Fair availability of advanced treatment plants for plastics waste	High availability of advanced treatment plants for plastics waste
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>

Functional clusterization of industries on territory

The location and level of aggregation of industrial areas on the territory influences the way and the possibility of implementing industrial synergies. For example, if industries are highly clustered within a country i.e.: they are concentrated in industrial areas, easily accessible, exchanges between them can be implemented with limited effort. On the other hand, if industries are typically spread in different locations, which can also be isolated, interconnections may turn complex from a logistic and technical perspective, resulting in increased costs and environmental burdens.

Answer Summary

The waste management department of the City of Torino concedes that for such information other departments or institutions could provide deeper insights. Industries with a circular economy focus or where certain synergies could be harnessed are likely to be found in dedicated industrial zones, forming clusters outside of the City's administrative area. It is added that the industrial landscape is in constant flux, as historic industries diminish and new ones emerge. The City's Chamber of Commerce⁷ would likely be able to provide more detailed information regarding industries that are or could be engaged in circular economy processes.

Functional clusterization of industries on territory			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Segmented clusterization: (industries are not properly interconnected)	Fair clusterization	High clusterization: (industries are efficiently interconnected)
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"			
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"			

⁷ <https://www.to.camcom.it/> (Accessed on 23.02.2020)

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Non-technical requirements

Existence of a market demand

A successful establishment of a value chain is triggered by the existence of a market demand for the end-products of the manufacturing process. Market demand is a crucial factor to positively activate and possibly sustain all the stages of each manufacturing chain. Within CIRCPACK project, a market analysis for the exploitation of the main results is performed. The analysis identifies categories of end users/customers potentially interested in the products obtained: as an example, manufacturers of primary, secondary, and tertiary plastic packaging may create demand for fully bio-degradable multilayer solutions and plastic packaging. The quantitative estimation of such demand can influence the decision of replicating a value chain in a certain country rather than in other.

Answer Summary

Citizens are interested in new environmentally sustainable products. The price-point of alternative products would probably have to be comparable to or lower than traditional less-sustainable products for them to gain significant market share under current conditions though.

In relation to public events held in the City of Torino there is certainly a high interest in moving away from single-use products. A switch has not been made mandatory and change is therefore only happening incrementally, however.

Existence of a market demand			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low end-users demand of bio-based products	Fair end-users demand of bio-based products	High end-users demand of bio-based products
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	Low end-users demand of recoverable products	Fair end-users demand of recoverable products	High end-users demand of recoverable products
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	Low manufacturers demand of secondary raw materials	Fair manufacturers demand of secondary raw materials	High manufacturers demand of secondary raw materials
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>

Support of governments to improve circular value chains: policy framework, financing and administrative burden

Opportunities and drivers promoted by governments may act as determinant facilitators for the implementation of circular economy strategies.

In recent years, several policy actions at EU level have been focusing on circular economy and associated business models. On 2 December 2015, the European Commission put forward a package to support the EU's transition to a circular economy. The EU Action Plan for the Circular Economy outlines a set of both general and material-specific actions.

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The circular economy has also gained momentum in the policies of Member States, largely due to the political priority given to it by the EU in recent years. Some MS have developed dedicated circular economy strategies and roadmaps (France, Netherlands, Finland, etc.). A growing number of regions (Flanders, the Basque country, etc.) are now acting to develop a circular economy and they have been joined by a number of cities (Amsterdam, London, etc.). Some have adopted circular economy strategies, while others have introduced the circular economy in their sectoral policies (waste, economy, agriculture, bio-economy, construction etc.).

The main enablers that can be offered with the aim of supporting the creation and development of circular value chain within a country include:

- the **enforcement of a consistent national policy framework**, effectively addressing responsibilities across all the stages of the value chains, involving all the interested stakeholders, from the manufacturing phase to waste collection and management and to reprocessing activities;
- the **financial and economic aspects of a project** are naturally crucial elements for replication. A sound project's financing analysis should be based on the evaluation, inter alia, of the following elements: financial costs, financial risks, hidden and unforeseen costs, and financial solutions. The allocation of national funds can facilitate and unlock the implementation of value chains presenting economic criticalities. They can be offered in form of incentives, tax reductions, grant, etc. A positive financial influence from governments contribute to increase innovative products' price competitiveness against traditional products on the market;
- **minimization of bureaucracy requirements** to get access to the available instruments, including an adequate presence of offices, hiring of sufficient appointed staff, online platform for remote access to services.

Answer Summary

Recycling policy is formulated at national level and incorporates European directives. Under the "CONAI System"⁸ six compulsory consortiums of manufacturers and recyclers have been formed, which accept waste resources such as steel, aluminium, paper, wood, plastic or glass for treatment and recycling. These consortia are managerially and organisationally autonomous, operating as private law, non-profit organisations. The ANCI-CONAI framework functions as a voluntary instrument via which the consortia and municipalities agree on details on the materials accepted, their recycling and the quality- and the quantity- level of remuneration for this was equal to the of conferred material.

A key driver for improvements to circular value chains could be national-level legislation to push regions, cities and private sector companies to step-up the production and use of biodegradable products for packaging, etc.

Due to the way in which waste management is governed in Italy, municipalities have comparatively little leverage to actively improve circular value chains. National legislation

⁸ <http://www.conai.org/en/about-us/conai-system/consortiums/> (Accessed on 21.02.2020)

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that incentivises circular economy approaches, which the CONAI consortia must implement is seen as the most likely pathway for any sectorial transformation.

There is popular support for financial incentives to bring down the cost of environmentally friendly products and incentivise waste reduction. Municipalities, however, are under significant budgetary pressures, which makes funding additional programs difficult. New public measures at local level would require the introduction of new taxes. In this context the City of Torino is contemplating to set up waste collection points that citizens can access via a card in about 3-4 years, so that taxation can be levied according to the volume of waste generated.

Support of governments to improve circular value chains			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Unfavourable policy context	Fair policy context	Encouraging policy context
	x	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Lack of financial support	Availability of financial support	Availability of consistent financial support
	x	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Complex and long bureaucracy requirements	Standard bureaucracy requirements	Easy-to-manage bureaucracy requirements
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	Unfavourable policy context	Fair policy context	Encouraging policy context
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Lack of financial support	Availability of financial support	Availability of consistent financial support
	x	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Complex and long bureaucracy requirements	Standard bureaucracy requirements	Easy-to-manage bureaucracy requirements
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	Unfavourable policy context	Fair policy context	Encouraging policy context
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Lack of financial support	Availability of financial support	Availability of consistent financial support
	x	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Complex and long bureaucracy requirements	Standard bureaucracy requirements	Easy-to-manage bureaucracy requirements
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>

Engagement of enterprises in promoting circular economy

In countries where enterprises and industries are traditionally engaged and interested in the creation of synergies and linkages, the realization of circular and innovative value chains

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can turn easier and more fruitful than under circumstances in which there is no interest for these strategies. In addition, a clear and concrete involvement of stakeholders in these mechanisms may encourage the development and implementation of actions of governments in the perspective of circular economy.

Answer Summary

The City of Torino promotes the use of re-usable and recyclable products, such as cups or cutlery, for events held in the city and has worked together with private sector companies to achieve tangible reductions in waste generation. In 2021 the municipality plans to introduce a certification scheme on sustainable and eco-friendly management of all events that it organises.

Engagement of enterprises in promoting circular economy			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low or none enterprises' effective commitment in circular economy implementation	Moderate enterprises' effective commitment in circular economy implementation	Notable enterprises' effective commitment in circular economy implementation
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"			
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"			
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>

Customers' awareness about circular economy and environmental

Customers have been reported as strong drivers for greening activities and their demands have a strong influence on the decisions that companies take towards eco-design. The level of awareness about circular economy principles among customers is important because it leads to the shifting of user buying intention towards environmentally friendly goods, determining the success of a value chain, which depends directly on the end-users demand, generated by their perception and satisfaction. If citizens are properly educated about environmental themes, such as green labelling, marketing and advertising, it is more likely that they purchase, consume products designed according to environmentally sustainable principles, even in those cases when they are not particularly competitive on the market. Moreover, it is also more likely that they are careful in implementing the suggested actions for proper end-of-life management.

Answer Summary

In the context of the Horizon 2020 project UrbanWINS⁹ the City of Torino set up "Urban Agoras" on recycling and reuse of materials, bringing together citizens, companies, researchers and other professionals to share and co-create local circular economy

⁹ <https://www.urbanwins.eu/torino/> (Accessed on 24.02.2020)

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approaches. The project has contributed to a greater awareness of environmental issues in general - and circular economy aspects in particular - in the city.

Engagement of enterprises in promoting circular economy			
	Low or none end-users' awareness about environmentally responsible purchases	Moderate end-users' awareness about environmentally responsible purchases	Notable end-users' awareness about environmentally responsible purchases
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"			
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"			
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"			
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>

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6.4 ANNEX D – ZAGREB INTERVIEW

Representative of Environment Department, City of Zagreb

Technical Requirements

Availability and relevance of local resources

CIRC-PACK value chains are univocally based on key products and flows. An easy availability of materials and substances necessary for their manufacturing is crucial to facilitate and generate the installation of suitable plants, as well as waste flows needed for the generation of secondary raw materials to feed the value chains are produced in sufficient amount within the country.

The availability and relevance of local resources is thus determinant to guarantee continuous and reliable supply to stakeholders involved in the manufacturing phases, while contributing to minimize costs (economic, environmental) sustained for duties, logistic and transport. Also from of a social perspective, the involvement of local actors has positive effects, as it can contribute to improve the social acceptance of the innovative products, by creating local employment.

Answer Summary:

The City of Zagreb currently collects around 216 kt of municipal solid waste (MSW) and around 130 kt of separately collected waste including paper, plastic, glass, wood, biowaste, bulky waste, textiles as well as electronic waste, batteries and tires (see also table below). While the MSW undergoes incineration (we do not have incineration) and landfill procedure, separately collectables are being recycled or in part incinerated.

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Type of waste	Amount	Total separately collected			Share
		From the municipal collection system	Waste at disposal sites / retailers of waste	Waste from service activities	
	(T)	(T)	(T)	(T)	%
Paper	37,857.76	10072.11	11913.91	15871.74	29.31
Plastic	5,024.77	3,539.56	108.40	1,376.81	3.89
Glass	2,584.23	2,305.05	0.00	279.18	2.00
Metal	9,804.63	220.02	9,390.44	194.17	7.59
Wood	7,348.17	6,283.26	0.00	1,064.91	5.69
Bulky waste	23,595.76	22149.75	0.00	1,446.01	18.27
Biowaste *	18540.18	1,582.73	0.00	16957.45	14,36
Textile	885.56	864.36	0.00	21,20	0.69
Electrical and electronic waste (EE waste)	9,491.99	942.63	7,756.62	792.74	7.35
Waste batteries and accumulators	272.62	4.13	266.78	1.71	0.21
Waste tires	354.63	189.08	165.55	0.00	0.27
Other	13390.11	1,655.90	8,706.39	3,027.82	10.37
IN TOTAL	129,150.41	49808.58	38308.09	41033.74	
Share (%)		38.57	29.66	31.77	

Table 29: Separately collected waste in the City of Zagreb (2018)

With regard to plastic- and organic/biowaste, the city has collected around 5 kt of plastic and around 18.5 kt of biowaste, including greening waste from municipal parks etc. Overall, the city has assessed the availability of local resources/feedstock (organic- and plastic waste) with respect to the three Circ-Pack demo-cases as fair, high, fair respective (please also see below).

Availability and relevance of local resources			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low availability of renewable feedstock <input type="checkbox"/>	Fair availability of renewable feedstock x	High availability of renewable feedstock <input type="checkbox"/>
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	Low availability of local resources <input type="checkbox"/>	Fair availability of local resources <input type="checkbox"/>	High availability of local resources x
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	Low availability of local resources <input type="checkbox"/>	Fair availability of local resources x	High availability of local resources <input type="checkbox"/>

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Waste collection and separation capacity

The capacity of collecting and sorting large amounts of waste is a driver for the implementation of successful and profitable value chains and symbioses. Such capacity derives from a combination of citizens' education to municipal waste management (or other wastes) and of the enforcement of efficient schemes for an adequate separate collection at municipal level. Proper collection and sorting have direct impact on waste reprocessing capacity and indirect impact on the availability of local resources.

Answer Summary

The city administration has the mandate to collect all kinds of waste (including MSW, separately collectables, EEW and hazardous waste). Thereby the city relies on three collection systems: door-to-door (especially for MSW, paper and biowaste), so called "green islands", i.e. dedicated neighborhood waste collection hubs (1000 in total) and recycling yards.

In the City of Zagreb, the collection of mixed municipal waste and biodegradable municipal waste and the separate collection of waste paper, metal, glass, plastics and textiles and large (bulky) waste are provided by the provider of public services and services related to public service - Zagreb Holding doo, Branch Office Cleanliness and other participants taking waste from public areas to ensure that waste is collected. From 2016, wastepaper and cardboard are collected separately at the doorstep, and from 2019, bio-waste and plastic and metal packaging. Bulk waste collection from households is organized at the request of the service user. All separately collected types of waste are submitted for further treatment to authorized recyclers.

For the fractions that are collected door-to-door, households are required to undertake pre-sorting (e.g. for paper and biowaste, plastic and metal). Glass and plastic are taken to the "green islands" and bulky waste as well as metals, minerals and greening waste to the recycling yards. For plastic waste (as for most fractions), the sorting after collection is contracted to two companies, "REOMA" and "Ce-Za-R d.o.o" which sort out 70% of the received quantity (e.g. 5 kt in 2018) as non-recyclable plastics.

For the organic waste fraction, around 18.5 kt were collected in 2018 through door-to-door and recycling yards for larger quantities. All of the biowaste is being processed further by one single private company – "Bioplinara Organica Kalnik".

The self-assessment with regard to the three CircPack demo-cases was done as demonstrated below.

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Waste collection and separation capacity			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants for bio-based plastics	Fair availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants for bio-based plastics	High availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants for bio-based plastics
	x	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	Low availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants	Fair availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants	High availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants
	x	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	Low availability of advanced separate collection schemes and sorting plants	Fair availability of advanced separate collection schemes and sorting plants	High availability of advanced separate collection schemes and sorting plants
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>

Waste reprocessing capacity

The technological capacity to reprocess multiple and large waste flows increases the potential of successful implementation of the value chains, allowing a greater availability of local resources (see previous requirement). Moreover, the presence of reprocessing plants is a proxy for the possibility of access –at local scale – to technologies and to technological background useful for the implementation of the desired value chains.

The reprocessing capacity is also valued at macro-scale level, waste reprocessing capacity is closely related to recovery and recycling rates for plastic and for packaging, which works as a transparent indicator for the availability of local resources, in terms of secondary raw materials and the possibility of recovering packaging waste at end-of-life.

Answer Summary

For the plastic fraction, the remaining 30% of sorted materials are being recycled into granulate etc. by the same two private companies responsible for sorting (REOMA and Ce-Za-R d.o.o), and are brought to the market for secondary raw materials, while a fraction is being reprocessed into new products by the companies themselves. The 70% non-recyclable materials (contaminated plastic, paper and organic fractions – mainly due to imperfect sorting in households, gastronomy and industry) are being processed by the same two companies into refuse derived fuel (RDF) and sold to the neighboring country Bosnia Herzegovina to be used there in the cement industry as fuel.

Regarding the organic waste fractions, Bioplinara Organica Kalnik produces biogase from corn silage around the region, digestant from biowaste to be used as fertilizer as well as biodegradable waste treatment. The company treats/reprocesses all the biowaste from the City of Zagreb.

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Waste reprocessing capacity			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low availability of treatment plants for bio-based plastics waste	Fair availability of treatment plants for bio-based plastics waste	High availability of treatment plants for bio-based plastics waste
	x	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	Low availability of treatment plants for plastics waste	Fair availability of treatment plants for plastics waste	High availability of treatment plants for plastics waste
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	Low availability of advanced treatment plants for plastics waste	Fair availability of advanced treatment plants for plastics waste	High availability of advanced treatment plants for plastics waste
	x	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Functional clusterization of industries on territory

The location and level of aggregation of industrial areas on the territory influences the way and the possibility of implementing industrial synergies. For example, if industries are highly clustered within a country i.e.: they are concentrated in industrial areas, easily accessible, exchanges between them can be implemented with limited effort. On the other hand, if industries are typically spread in different locations, which can also be isolated, interconnections may turn complex from a logistic and technical perspective, resulting in increased costs and environmental burdens.

Answer Summary

The clusterization of industries involved in the plastics value chain in Zagreb is quite scattered. Only a few steps of the value chain are interconnected. However the combined sorting and reprocessing capacity of the two companies REOMA and Ce-Za-R is working towards a more closed cycle. Market actors for the secondary materials market are not strongly connected to the recyclers. Moreover, a big portion of the plastic collectables are being exported outside of Croatia. The situation with third party market actors (e.g. companies using recycled plastic granulate) could not be described in the interview.

For the bio-waste value chain, actors are very centralized with Bioplinara Organica Kalnik being the only company collecting all the biowaste from the City of Zagreb. However, the plant is around 100 km away from the city.

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Functional clusterization of industries on territory			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Segmented clusterization: (industries are not properly interconnected)	Fair clusterization	High clusterization: (industries are efficiently interconnected)
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	x	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"			

Non-technical requirements

Existence of a market demand

A successful establishment of a value chain is triggered by the existence of a market demand for the end-products of the manufacturing process. Market demand is a crucial factor to positively activate and possibly sustain all the stages of each manufacturing chain. Within CIRCPACK project, a market analysis for the exploitation of the main results is performed. The analysis identifies categories of end users/customers potentially interested in the products obtained: as an example, manufacturers of primary, secondary, and tertiary plastic packaging may create demand for fully bio-degradable multilayer solutions and plastic packaging. The quantitative estimation of such demand can influence the decision of replicating a value chain in a certain country rather than in other.

Answer Summary

The status quo with regard to market demand for secondary plastics or bio-based plastics could not be described due to a lack of information on the topic. Overall, a "good response" towards these products by retailers and customers was estimated. Moreover, several initiatives were named (see requirement on engagement below). For more detailed estimations with regard to the CircPack demo-cases, see below.

Existence of a market demand			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low end-users demand of bio-based products	Fair end-users demand of bio-based products	High end-users demand of bio-based products
	x	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	Low end-users demand of recoverable products	Fair end-users demand of recoverable products	High end-users demand of recoverable products
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	Low manufacturers demand of secondary raw materials	Fair manufacturers demand of secondary raw materials	High manufacturers demand of secondary raw materials
	x	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

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Support of governments to improve circular value chains: policy framework, financing and administrative burden

Opportunities and drivers promoted by governments may act as determinant facilitators for the implementation of circular economy strategies.

In recent years, several policy actions at EU level have been focusing on circular economy and associated business models. On 2 December 2015, the European Commission put forward a package to support the EU's transition to a circular economy. The EU Action Plan for the Circular Economy outlines a set of both general and material-specific actions.

The circular economy has also gained momentum in the policies of Members States, largely due to the political priority given to it by the EU in recent years. Some MS have developed dedicated circular economy strategies and roadmaps (France, Netherlands, Finland, etc.). A growing number of regions (Flanders, the Basque country, etc.) are now acting to develop a circular economy and they have been joined by a number of cities (Amsterdam, London, etc.). Some have adopted circular economy strategies, while others have introduced the circular economy in their sectoral policies (waste, economy, agriculture, bio-economy, construction etc.).

The main enablers that can be offered with the aim of supporting the creation and development of circular value chain within a country include:

- the **enforcement of a consistent national policy framework**, effectively addressing responsibilities across all the stages of the value chains, involving all the interested stakeholders, from the manufacturing phase to waste collection and management and to reprocessing activities;
- the **financial and economic aspects of a project** are naturally crucial elements for replication. A sound project's financing analysis should be based on the evaluation, inter alia, of the following elements: financial costs, financial risks, hidden and unforeseen costs, and financial solutions. The allocation of national funds can facilitate and unlock the implementation of value chains presenting economic criticalities. They can be offered in form of incentives, tax reductions, grant, etc. A positive financial influence from governments contribute to increase innovative products' price competitiveness against traditional products on the market;
- **minimization of bureaucracy requirements** to get access to the available instruments, including an adequate presence of offices, hiring of sufficient appointed staff, online platform for remote access to services.

Answer Summary

As the basic strategic framework, the City of Zagreb has a Waste Management Plan from 2018 as the follow-up to two prior plans by two different Ministers. The plan is largely based on the EU Waste Directive as well as the Circular Economy Package (2015) and tries to speed-up the waste agenda in Zagreb.

There is no specific national financing (we have EU/national financing) for improving the waste management at the local or regional scale in Croatia, which is why the City of Zagreb is currently engaged in at least three European projects on the topic. Additionally, there are EU cohesion and other regional funds available, which the city plans to invest mainly in three

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large-scale projects: (1) the building of a municipal waste management center, (2) building of a sorting plant as well as (3) a biowaste treatment plant in- or close to Zagreb.

Support of governments to improve circular value chains			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Unfavourable policy context	Fair policy context	Encouraging policy context
	x	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Lack of financial support	Availability of financial support	Availability of consistent financial support
	x	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Complex and long bureaucracy requirements	Standard bureaucracy requirements	Easy-to-manage bureaucracy requirements
<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>	
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	Unfavourable policy context	Fair policy context	Encouraging policy context
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Lack of financial support	Availability of financial support	Availability of consistent financial support
	x	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Complex and long bureaucracy requirements	Standard bureaucracy requirements	Easy-to-manage bureaucracy requirements
<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>	
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	Unfavourable policy context	Fair policy context	Encouraging policy context
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Lack of financial support	Availability of financial support	Availability of consistent financial support
	x	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Complex and long bureaucracy requirements	Standard bureaucracy requirements	Easy-to-manage bureaucracy requirements
<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>	

Engagement of enterprises in promoting circular economy

In countries where enterprises and industries are traditionally engaged and interested in the creation of synergies and linkages, the realization of circular and innovative value chains can turn easier and more fruitful than under circumstances in which there is no interest for these strategies. In addition, a clear and concrete involvement of stakeholders in these mechanisms may encourage the development and implementation of actions of governments in the perspective of circular economy.

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Answer Summary

Engagement of large-scale industries along the value chain could not be discussed due to a lack of information or related studies. However, a number of smaller scale, innovative initiatives were mentioned:

- Engagement of innovative companies in Zagreb within the “Climate KIC Regional Hub”
- Municipal reuse center, where furniture, electric equipment etc. can be taken by citizens and is repaired or remanufactured on site. The center also includes a social component and serves artists and creative branches as local hub. *To be built.*
- Single use cups have been banned at events and festival of the city with the engagement of local companies.

Engagement of enterprises in promoting circular economy			
DC-A “Plastics from renewable resources”	Low or none enterprises' effective commitment in circular economy implementation	Moderate enterprises' effective commitment in circular economy implementation	Notable enterprises' effective commitment in circular economy implementation
DC-B “Eco-friendly packaging design”			
DC-C “Enhanced sorting and recycling”			
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>

Customers' awareness about circular economy and environmental

Customers have been reported as strong drivers for greening activities and their demands have a strong influence on the decisions that companies take towards eco-design.

The level of awareness about circular economy principles among customers is important because it leads to the shifting of user buying intention towards environmentally friendly goods, determining the success of a value chain, which depends directly on the end-users demand, generated by their perception and satisfaction. If citizens are properly educated about environmental themes, such as green labelling, marketing and advertising, it is more likely that they purchase, consume products designed according to environmentally sustainable principles, even in those cases when they are not particularly competitive on the market. Moreover, it is also more likely that they are careful in implementing the suggested actions for proper end-of-life management.

Answer Summary

No concrete points could be discussed due to a lack of information or related studies. Generally, customer awareness on the topics was estimate low, but in change towards a better understanding of the benefits of such products.

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Engagement of enterprises in promoting circular economy			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low or none end-users' awareness about environmentally responsible purchases	Moderate end-users' awareness about environmentally responsible purchases	Notable end-users' awareness about environmentally responsible purchases
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"			
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"			
	x	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

- **Considering the replicability self-assessment for all the requirements, overall, which demo case would you consider to be replicable in your local area?** (more than one answer can be provided)
 - DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"
 - DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"
 - x DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"

- **For the demo case(s) you considered as replicable, could you suggest one or more specific value chains (among those covered by the project, or similar) suitable to be implemented in the area of your city?**

The first two demo cases are more for private companies. For the City of Zagreb, it might be applicable the demo case C Enhanced Sorting and recycling / creating an effective after-use plastics economy.

It is very important to educate the population from kindergartens, schools, businesses, tourists and everyone else. Namely, in order to achieve the highest possible degree of separation of waste and to make the waste as "quality and clean" as possible for further processing, additional efforts need to be made to create clean environmental awareness. Much has been done in the last few years, but only when we finish building the necessary municipal infrastructure than we will have a closed cycle in the waste management system. At that point, City of Zagreb will be able to give greater importance to the circular economy as well.

The construction of municipal infrastructure will establish the best available technology for waste treatment and the results of the treatment will be better and the City of Zagreb will fulfill its obligations for separate waste collection.

In parallel, work should be done to strengthen the private sector, which, in addition to urban municipal infrastructure, will be an additional element in waste treatment, such as using a new formulation of secondary raw materials generated in a recycling plant.

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- **Finally, which local actors would you identify to represent relevant roles in the possible implementation of such circular value chain(s)?**

The main stakeholders in this process would be the City of Zagreb and Holding, which would coordinate activities to establish a better quality waste management system. With them, a very important part would be related to information and education. And the third part of the stakeholders are those who would take this new raw material and continue to use it in production

Please amend the scheme proposed for the demo-cases you assessed as suitable for replicability by including local actors you would consider suitable to be integrated in a circular plastic packaging value chain.

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DEMO CASE C “Enhanced sorting and recycling”

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6.5 ANNEX E – FREIBURG INTERVIEW

Representative of ASF municipal waste management company

Technical Requirements

Availability and relevance of local resources

CIRC-PACK value chains are univocally based on key products and flows. An easy availability of materials and substances necessary for their manufacturing is crucial to facilitate and generate the installation of suitable plants, as well as waste flows needed for the generation of secondary raw materials to feed the value chains are produced in sufficient amount within the country.

The availability and relevance of local resources is thus determinant to guarantee continuous and reliable supply to stakeholders involved in the manufacturing phases, while contributing to minimize costs (economic, environmental) sustained for duties, logistic and transport. Also from of a social perspective, the involvement of local actors has positive effects, as it can contribute to improve the social acceptance of the innovative products, by creating local employment.

Answer Summary:

Based on the waste management concept from 2015, the City of Freiburg collected around 85 kt (389.2 kg/cap) of waste including paper, plastic, glass, wood, biowaste, bulky waste, textiles as well as electronic waste, batteries and tires (see also table below). While the MSW (or residual waste) undergoes incineration, separately collectables are being recycled or in part incinerated.

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Waste for valuation per resident	Freiburg 2013	Baden-Württemberg 2013
Organic waste	66 kg	45 kg
Green waste	48 kg	85 kg
LVP	24 kg	27 kg
PPK	93 kg	83 kg
Glass	29 kg	26 kg
Metal	5,2 kg	9,7 kg
Plastic	2,2 kg	7,9 kg
Old electronic & electric appliances	7,8 kg	7,6 kg
Total waste for valuation	277,2 kg	291,2 kg
Abfall zur Beseitigung pro Ew.		
Residual waste	94 kg	123 kg
Bulky waste	18 kg	21 kg
Total waste for disposal	112 kg	144 kg
Total waste	389,2 kg	435,2 kg

Table 30: Total waste collected per capita in the City of Freiburg and the province of Baden-Wuerttemberg (2013)

With regard to plastic- and organic/biowaste, the city has collected around 5.2 kt (24 kg/cap) of plastic packaging waste and around 26.3 kt (114 kg/cap) of biowaste, including greening waste from municipal parks etc. Overall, the city has assessed the availability of local resources/feedstock (organic- and plastic waste) with respect to the three Circ-Pack demo-cases as fair, high, fair respective (please also see below).

Availability and relevance of local resources			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low availability of renewable feedstock	Fair availability of renewable feedstock	High availability of renewable feedstock
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	Low availability of local resources	Fair availability of local resources	High availability of local resources
	x	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	Low availability of local resources	Fair availability of local resources	High availability of local resources
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>

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Waste collection and separation capacity

The capacity of collecting and sorting large amounts of waste is a driver for the implementation of successful and profitable value chains and symbioses. Such capacity derives from a combination of citizens' education to municipal waste management (or other wastes) and of the enforcement of efficient schemes for an adequate separate collection at municipal level. Proper collection and sorting have direct impact on waste reprocessing capacity and indirect impact on the availability of local resources.

Answer Summary

The "Abfallwirtschaft Freiburg" (ASF), in majority owned by the City of Freiburg, has the mandate to collect all kinds of waste, including for households MSW, paper, packaging, bio-waste. Industrial waste is up for competition, but depending on the company/facility, ASF will cover all waste fractions here as well. For the household waste the city relies on three collection systems: door-to-door (e.g. for MSW, paper, biowaste and light weight packaging), public containers (e.g. for glass) and recycling yards (mainly for construction waste, green waste, bulky waste and EEW)

For the fractions that are collected door-to-door, households are required to undertake pre-sorting (i.e. for paper, lightweight packaging and biowaste). Glass is being disposed of in public containers and bulky waste as well as metals, minerals and greening waste goes to the recycling yards.

For lightweight packaging waste, the waste is being collected by ASF and brought to facilities of the REMONDIS company. From there, the waste is distributed for sorting and recycling. The sorting and recycling is subject to the so-called dual system in Germany (see next requirement on reprocessing capacity below). A major part of the packaging waste from the City of Freiburg is going to "Vogt Plastik" (Rheinfeld, approx. 75 km away from Freiburg) for recycling and re-manufacturing.

For the organic waste fraction, around 26.3 kt were collected in 2015 through door-to-door and recycling yards (for larger quantities). All of the biowaste is being processed further the city owned company RETERRA.

The self-assessment with regard to the three CircPack demo-cases was done as demonstrated below.

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Waste collection and separation capacity			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants for bio-based plastics	Fair availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants for bio-based plastics	High availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants for bio-based plastics
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	Low availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants	Fair availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants	High availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	Low availability of advanced separate collection schemes and sorting plants	Fair availability of advanced separate collection schemes and sorting plants	High availability of advanced separate collection schemes and sorting plants
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>

Waste reprocessing capacity

The technological capacity to reprocess multiple and large waste flows increases the potential of successful implementation of the value chains, allowing a greater availability of local resources (see previous requirement). Moreover, the presence of reprocessing plants is a proxy for the possibility of access –at local scale – to technologies and to technological background useful for the implementation of the desired value chains.

The reprocessing capacity is also valued at macro-scale level, waste reprocessing capacity is closely related to recovery and recycling rates for plastic and for packaging, which works as a transparent indicator for the availability of local resources, in terms of secondary raw materials and the possibility of recovering packaging waste at end-of-life.

Answer Summary

In Germany, reprocessing of lightweight packaging is subject to the so-called "dual system" (introduced in 1990ies). The system comprises of (currently) seven companies. Customers, when purchasing a packaged product, pay a certain fee that is integrated in the end price of the product. All fees collected in Germany go to a central administrative body of the dual system, which manages and distributes the funds across the different seven competitors within the dual system, depending on the territory they cover. The administrative body will from time to time issue a bid for taking the waste from certain districts that have run out of contract coverage. Companies of the dual system can apply for these and, should they get the bid, will receive all the packaging waste from this district as well as the proportionate fees collected as part of the product prize. Thereby, the companies have no control over the exact quantity nor quality of the waste received. The steps of the value chain covered, as well the treatment options applied by the dual systems, are not necessary aligned, which means that one company could be going as far as plastic granulate production and even (re)manufacturing of new products, while some other system may only sort the waste and sell it. The crucial point is that these companies receive the waste and the proportionate fee and are thus responsible for its treatment.

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For the Freiburg case, this means that after collection of packaging waste through ASF and interim storage at REMONDIS. The waste is going to a dual system (or more than one) that operates everywhere in Germany. Quality and quantity of packaging waste treated is hence not clear as the information is not shared by the dual system. For Freiburg, however, "Vogt Plastik" recycles most of the packaging waste.

For organic waste, all waste is being processed by city-owned facility RETERRA. Main treatment output is biomethane.

Waste reprocessing capacity			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low availability of treatment plants for bio-based plastics waste	Fair availability of treatment plants for bio-based plastics waste	High availability of treatment plants for bio-based plastics waste
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	x
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	Low availability of treatment plants for plastics waste	Fair availability of treatment plants for plastics waste	High availability of treatment plants for plastics waste
	x	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	Low availability of advanced treatment plants for plastics waste	Fair availability of advanced treatment plants for plastics waste	High availability of advanced treatment plants for plastics waste
	x	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Functional clusterization of industries on territory

The location and level of aggregation of industrial areas on the territory influences the way and the possibility of implementing industrial synergies. For example, if industries are highly clustered within a country i.e.: they are concentrated in industrial areas, easily accessible, exchanges between them can be implemented with limited effort. On the other hand, if industries are typically spread in different locations, which can also be isolated, interconnections may turn complex from a logistic and technical perspective, resulting in increased costs and environmental burdens.

Answer Summary

(see answer summary above on Waste reprocessing capacity)

Functional clusterization of industries on territory			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Segmented clusterization: (industries are not properly interconnected)	Fair clusterization	High clusterization: (industries are efficiently interconnected)
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	x	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"			

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Non-technical requirements

Existence of a market demand

A successful establishment of a value chain is triggered by the existence of a market demand for the end-products of the manufacturing process. Market demand is a crucial factor to positively activate and possibly sustain all the stages of each manufacturing chain. Within CIRCPACK project, a market analysis for the exploitation of the main results is performed. The analysis identifies categories of end users/customers potentially interested in the products obtained: as an example, manufacturers of primary, secondary, and tertiary plastic packaging may create demand for fully bio-degradable multilayer solutions and plastic packaging. The quantitative estimation of such demand can influence the decision of replicating a value chain in a certain country rather than in other.

Answer Summary

The status quo with regard to market demand for secondary plastics or bio-based plastics could not be described due to a lack of information on the topic. Overall, a “good response” towards these products by retailers and customers was estimated. For more detailed estimations with regard to the CircPack demo-cases, see below.

Existence of a market demand			
DC-A “Plastics from renewable resources”	Low end-users demand of bio-based products	Fair end-users demand of bio-based products	High end-users demand of bio-based products
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	x
DC-B “Eco-friendly packaging design”	Low end-users demand of recoverable products	Fair end-users demand of recoverable products	High end-users demand of recoverable products
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	x
DC-C “Enhanced sorting and recycling”	Low manufacturers demand of secondary raw materials	Fair manufacturers demand of secondary raw materials	High manufacturers demand of secondary raw materials
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>

Support of governments to improve circular value chains: policy framework, financing and administrative burden

Opportunities and drivers promoted by governments may act as determinant facilitators for the implementation of circular economy strategies.

In recent years, several policy actions at EU level have been focusing on circular economy and associated business models. On 2 December 2015, the European Commission put forward a package to support the EU's transition to a circular economy. The EU Action Plan for the Circular Economy outlines a set of both general and material-specific actions.

The circular economy has also gained momentum in the policies of Member States, largely due to the political priority given to it by the EU in recent years. Some MS have developed dedicated circular economy strategies and roadmaps (France, Netherlands, Finland, etc.). A growing number of regions (Flanders, the Basque country, etc.) are now acting to develop a circular economy and they have been joined by a number of cities (Amsterdam, London,

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etc.). Some have adopted circular economy strategies, while others have introduced the circular economy in their sectoral policies (waste, economy, agriculture, bio-economy, construction etc.).

The main enablers that can be offered with the aim of supporting the creation and development of circular value chain within a country include:

- the **enforcement of a consistent national policy framework**, effectively addressing responsibilities across all the stages of the value chains, involving all the interested stakeholders, from the manufacturing phase to waste collection and management and to reprocessing activities;
- the **financial and economic aspects of a project** are naturally crucial elements for replication. A sound project's financing analysis should be based on the evaluation, inter alia, of the following elements: financial costs, financial risks, hidden and unforeseen costs, and financial solutions. The allocation of national funds can facilitate and unlock the implementation of value chains presenting economic criticalities. They can be offered in form of incentives, tax reductions, grant, etc. A positive financial influence from governments contribute to increase innovative products' price competitiveness against traditional products on the market;
- **minimization of bureaucracy requirements** to get access to the available instruments, including an adequate presence of offices, hiring of sufficient appointed staff, online platform for remote access to services.

Answer Summary

The City of Freiburg has Waste Management Concept from 2015 that highlights the city's own ambition, setting targets and perspectives for the future. The city is currently working on new concept that will introduce new plans, specifically with regard to boosting the circular economy. However, the focus areas for the new plan will be waste reduction and better waste separation. The "Abfallsatzung" (Engl. Waste Charter) is a legal document for the local level in Germany which determines waste flows, quantities, treatment options, fees etc. and is the most important legal instrument in waste management. However, besides the concept, there are only few regulatory levers at the local level.

National and regional waste regulation in Germany is based on EU law (e.g. the EU Waste Directive and the EU Circular Economy Package). There is some regional funding (e.g. in Baden Wuerttemberg to go into material recovery with organic waste (e.g. bio-polymerization), however hurdles are still high.

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Support of governments to improve circular value chains			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Unfavourable policy context	Fair policy context	Encouraging policy context
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Lack of financial support	Availability of financial support	Availability of consistent financial support
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	Complex and long bureaucracy requirements	Standard bureaucracy requirements	Easy-to-manage bureaucracy requirements
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Unfavourable policy context	Fair policy context	Encouraging policy context
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	Lack of financial support	Availability of financial support	Availability of consistent financial support
	x	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Complex and long bureaucracy requirements	Standard bureaucracy requirements	Easy-to-manage bureaucracy requirements
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>

Engagement of enterprises in promoting circular economy

In countries where enterprises and industries are traditionally engaged and interested in the creation of synergies and linkages, the realization of circular and innovative value chains can turn easier and more fruitful than under circumstances in which there is no interest for these strategies. In addition, a clear and concrete involvement of stakeholders in these mechanisms may encourage the development and implementation of actions of governments in the perspective of circular economy.

Answer Summary

In general, for the plastic packaging waste, there is little the city or its companies engaged in waste management can do to actively promote the use of secondary raw materials unless the city would cover more steps in the plastics value chain (not only collection). In

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the case of Freiburg, everything else occurs outside of the city's territory and through other companies that operate nation- and Europe-wide. What the city can currently advocate for is the reduction- and separation of waste.

Engagement of enterprises in promoting circular economy			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low or none enterprises' effective commitment in circular economy implementation	Moderate enterprises' effective commitment in circular economy implementation	Notable enterprises' effective commitment in circular economy implementation
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"			
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>

Customers' awareness about circular economy and environmental

Customers have been reported as strong drivers for greening activities and their demands have a strong influence on the decisions that companies take towards eco-design. The level of awareness about circular economy principles among customers is important because it leads to the shifting of user buying intention towards environmentally friendly goods, determining the success of a value chain, which depends directly on the end-users demand, generated by their perception and satisfaction. If citizens are properly educated about environmental themes, such as green labelling, marketing and advertising, it is more likely that they purchase, consume products designed according to environmentally sustainable principles, even in those cases when they are not particularly competitive on the market. Moreover, it is also more likely that they are careful in implementing the suggested actions for proper end-of-life management.

Answer Summary

No concrete information has been discussed due to a lack information or relevant studies. In general, the awareness among the population is estimated quite high. Freiburg is known in Germany for having many citizens conscious to the causal relationships between resource consumption and environmental pressures and hence are deemed open to buying recycled packaging or biodegradable plastic in general.

Engagement of enterprises in promoting circular economy			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low or none end-users' awareness about environmentally responsible purchases	Moderate end-users' awareness about environmentally responsible purchases	Notable end-users' awareness about environmentally responsible purchases
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"			
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	x

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6.6 ANNEX F – SEVILLA INTERVIEW

Representative of LIPASAM municipal waste management company

Technical Requirements

Availability and relevance of local resources

CIRC-PACK value chains are univocally based on key products and flows. An easy availability of materials and substances necessary for their manufacturing is crucial to facilitate and generate the installation of suitable plants, as well as waste flows needed for the generation of secondary raw materials to feed the value chains are produced in sufficient amount within the country.

The availability and relevance of local resources is thus determinant to guarantee continuous and reliable supply to stakeholders involved in the manufacturing phases, while contributing to minimize costs (economic, environmental) sustained for duties, logistic and transport. Also from of a social perspective, the involvement of local actors has positive effects, as it can contribute to improve the social acceptance of the innovative products, by creating local employment.

Answer Summary

5 Fractions:

Tons selective collection	2019
Glass	10.359
Paper & Board	12.635
Light-packaging	8.301
Bio-waste	1.776
Total amount of selective collection	33.071

Availability and relevance of local resources			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low availability of renewable feedstock	Fair availability of renewable feedstock	High availability of renewable feedstock
	X	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	Low availability of local resources	Fair availability of local resources	High availability of local resources
	<input type="checkbox"/>	X	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	Low availability of local resources	Fair availability of local resources	High availability of local resources
	<input type="checkbox"/>	X	<input type="checkbox"/>

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Waste collection and separation capacity

The capacity of collecting and sorting large amounts of waste is a driver for the implementation of successful and profitable value chains and symbioses. Such capacity derives from a combination of citizens' education to municipal waste management (or other wastes) and of the enforcement of efficient schemes for an adequate separate collection at municipal level. Proper collection and sorting have direct impact on waste reprocessing capacity and indirect impact on the availability of local resources.

Answer Summary

Plastics (Lightpackaging).

LIPASAM as a municipal company responsible for the collection of municipal waste in Seville is adhered to the Framework Agreement signed between the FAMP (Andalusian Federation of Municipalities and Provinces), Consejería de Medio Ambiente de Andalucía (Environmental Regional Authority) and Ecoembes, who is a system collective of extended responsibility of the producer of the packaged products that are put on the market. This framework agreement regulates the requirements that correspond to the municipal collection of household .Domestic lightpackaging waste are understood to be those coming from households and similar ones although come from commercial origin, but the have to be similar in quantity and nature to households ones, according to the applicable Municipal rule. Lightpackaging waste of industrial or commercial origin that exceed the quantities established in the Seville rule are the responsibility of their producers, who must manage them with authorized waste managers. The estimation of plastic waste generated in the commercial and industrial flow in Seville are:

Plastics	Tons/year
PET	1.494
PEAD	812
PVC	1,3
PEDB	1.171
Other plastics	617
Total	4.095

Plastic Collection by LIPASAM

LIPASAM for the collection of this waste has the following collection systems available for citizens:

- Yellow-marked containers in the street: 2,426 units with a total of 6,712,120 l of capacity.
- Pneumatic collection containers: 344 units.
- Additionally, LIPASAM collects this waste at different events in the city, having started in 2019 a pilot selective collection test of this waste in a part of the "Feria de Abril de Sevilla". Once the waste are collected, they are transported to the lighpackaging classification plant, managed by ABORGASE S.A. which is about 20 km far from the city.

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Organic Waste

LIPASAM do the selective collection of organic waste (bio-waste), having begun in 2017. Currently, the following are collected:

- 18 Municipal markets.
- 3 large hospitals
- 5 hotels
- 2 routes of containers in the street using electronic card.

In total there are 383 containers and in 2019 a total of 1,776 tons have been collected.

Waste collection and separation capacity			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants for bio-based plastics	Fair availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants for bio-based plastics	High availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants for bio-based plastics
	<input type="checkbox"/>	X	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	Low availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants	Fair availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants	High availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants
	<input type="checkbox"/>	X	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	Low availability of advanced separate collection schemes and sorting plants	Fair availability of advanced separate collection schemes and sorting plants	High availability of advanced separate collection schemes and sorting plants
	<input type="checkbox"/>	X	<input type="checkbox"/>

Waste reprocessing capacity

The technological capacity to reprocess multiple and large waste flows increases the potential of successful implementation of the value chains, allowing a greater availability of local resources (see previous requirement). Moreover, the presence of reprocessing plants is a proxy for the possibility of access –at local scale – to technologies and to technological background useful for the implementation of the desired value chains.

The reprocessing capacity is also valued at macro-scale level, waste reprocessing capacity is closely related to recovery and recycling rates for plastic and for packaging, which works as a transparent indicator for the availability of local resources, in terms of secondary raw materials and the possibility of recovering packaging waste at end-of-life.

Answer Summary

Plastics:

The plastics, once they are packaged in the sorting plant, are sold to different recyclers. In the province of Seville there are mainly 2 for this waste stream:

- Reciclados la Red.
- Reciclados y recuperados del Sur.

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Both recyclers create pellets, and this in turn is sold to packaging manufacturers.

Organic waste

The selectively collected organic waste is sent to the treatment plant for its recovery as compost. This treatment plant is managed by ABORGASE S.A. , and is located about 20 km from Seville.Waste treatment is:

The waste is transported to a 110 mm trommel hopper. In the trommel the "rejection" which have a greater size than 110 mm is separated. The trommel "fines" are transported by conveyor belt to the fermentation hall, where they are deposited in an independent plot separated from any other residue.

Once the first fermentation and self-heating phases have been reached for a minimum of 15 days, in which due to high temperatures (70°C) pathogenic germs, weed seeds and insect larvae are eliminated, turned to oxygenate and introduced into the second sieve, or trommel with a diameter of 35 mm, the sunken of which is transported or transferred to the maturing hall.

The maturing stay is about 6 months, during which the high temperatures are lost, it is turned to improve the oxidation conditions, and the composting process is completed, intervening throughout this process, some sequences of microorganisms and fungi whose end result is the stability of the compost. Once this maturation period has passed, the compost will go through a 15 mm sieve and a densimetric table, which will leave the final compost free of impurities such as stones, or glass ceramic remains.This final compost will also be subjected to various analyzes, prior to shipment, including the maturity test and all the parameters necessary for its cataloging as a useful organic amendment for the improvement of the soils of the cultivation fields and its enrichment in nutrients for the vegetables.

Waste reprocessing capacity			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low availability of treatment plants for bio-based plastics waste	Fair availability of treatment plants for bio-based plastics waste	High availability of treatment plants for bio-based plastics waste
	<input type="checkbox"/>	X	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	Low availability of treatment plants for plastics waste	Fair availability of treatment plants for plastics waste	High availability of treatment plants for plastics waste
	<input type="checkbox"/>	X	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	Low availability of advanced treatment plants for plastics waste	Fair availability of advanced treatment plants for plastics waste	High availability of advanced treatment plants for plastics waste
	<input type="checkbox"/>	X	<input type="checkbox"/>

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Functional clusterization of industries on territory

The location and level of aggregation of industrial areas on the territory influences the way and the possibility of implementing industrial synergies. For example, if industries are highly clustered within a country i.e.: they are concentrated in industrial areas, easily accessible, exchanges between them can be implemented with limited effort. On the other hand, if industries are typically spread in different locations, which can also be isolated, interconnections may turn complex from a logistic and technical perspective, resulting in increased costs and environmental burdens.

Answer Summary

LIPASAM

As has been said, LIPASAM is the company of the Seville City Council in charge of collecting municipal waste of household origin or similar to domestic waste from other producers.

Mancomunidad de Los Alcores.

It groups different municipalities, including the city of Seville. Responsible for the treatment of waste from its area of influence. Collaborate with the different municipalities.

Waste producers

- Households: collected by LIPASAM
- Commercial and industrial: They must deliver them to authorized waste managers.

SCRAP

Extended producer responsibility systems. For the waste that SCRAP is constituted, these are ultimately responsible for waste management, establishing agreements and covenants are the local entities and with Consejería de Medio Ambiente de Andalucía (Environmental Regional Authority).

Waste managers

Responsible for the various phases of waste management (collection when appropriate, classification, storage and treatment). For example: ABORGASE.

Recyclers.

Companies whose business consists of putting back on the market the waste received from the different previous agents. For example: Recicladores La Red.

Functional clusterization of industries on territory			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Segmented clusterization: (industries are not properly interconnected)	Fair clusterization	High clusterization: (industries are efficiently interconnected)
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"		X	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	<input type="checkbox"/>		

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Non-technical requirements

Existence of a market demand

A successful establishment of a value chain is triggered by the existence of a market demand for the end-products of the manufacturing process. Market demand is a crucial factor to positively activate and possibly sustain all the stages of each manufacturing chain. Within CIRCPACK project, a market analysis for the exploitation of the main results is performed. The analysis identifies categories of end users/customers potentially interested in the products obtained: as an example, manufacturers of primary, secondary, and tertiary plastic packaging may create demand for fully bio-degradable multilayer solutions and plastic packaging. The quantitative estimation of such demand can influence the decision of replicating a value chain in a certain country rather than in other.

For some of the municipal waste that LIPASAM collects, there are recycling companies nearby that later put their products on the market:

- Plastics
- Metals
- Paper-cardboard
- Glass
- Woods
- Pruning
- Organic waste
- Cooked oil used
- Textiles
- WEEE
- Batteries

Existence of a market demand			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low end-users demand of bio-based products	Fair end-users demand of bio-based products	High end-users demand of bio-based products
	<input type="checkbox"/>	X	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	Low end-users demand of recoverable products	Fair end-users demand of recoverable products	High end-users demand of recoverable products
	X	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	Low manufacturers demand of secondary raw materials	Fair manufacturers demand of secondary raw materials	High manufacturers demand of secondary raw materials
	<input type="checkbox"/>	X	<input type="checkbox"/>

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Support of governments to improve circular value chains: policy framework, financing and administrative burden

Opportunities and drivers promoted by governments may act as determinant facilitators for the implementation of circular economy strategies.

In recent years, several policy actions at EU level have been focusing on circular economy and associated business models. On 2 December 2015, the European Commission put forward a package to support the EU's transition to a circular economy. The EU Action Plan for the Circular Economy outlines a set of both general and material-specific actions.

The circular economy has also gained momentum in the policies of Members States, largely due to the political priority given to it by the EU in recent years. Some MS have developed dedicated circular economy strategies and roadmaps (France, Netherlands, Finland, etc.). A growing number of regions (Flanders, the Basque country, etc.) are now acting to develop a circular economy and they have been joined by a number of cities (Amsterdam, London, etc.). Some have adopted circular economy strategies, while others have introduced the circular economy in their sectoral policies (waste, economy, agriculture, bio-economy, construction etc.).

The main enablers that can be offered with the aim of supporting the creation and development of circular value chain within a country include:

- the **enforcement of a consistent national policy framework**, effectively addressing responsibilities across all the stages of the value chains, involving all the interested stakeholders, from the manufacturing phase to waste collection and management and to reprocessing activities;
- the **financial and economic aspects of a project** are naturally crucial elements for replication. A sound project's financing analysis should be based on the evaluation, inter alia, of the following elements: financial costs, financial risks, hidden and unforeseen costs, and financial solutions. The allocation of national funds can facilitate and unlock the implementation of value chains presenting economic criticalities. They can be offered in form of incentives, tax reductions, grant, etc. A positive financial influence from governments contribute to increase innovative products' price competitiveness against traditional products on the market;
- **minimization of bureaucracy requirements** to get access to the available instruments, including an adequate presence of offices, hiring of sufficient appointed staff, online platform for remote access to services.

Answer Summary

In my opinion, these are still incipient processes, which must grow in the medium and long term. In Spain there are regional differences, since some regions are more advanced.

Recently, frameworks, strategies, agreements have been created, but their materialization in concrete measures is lacking, and the impact of these in both the public and private sectors.

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In the city of Seville, the circular economy processes are not sufficiently studied, so we lack enough information.

Support of governments to improve circular value chains			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Unfavourable policy context	Fair policy context	Encouraging policy context
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Lack of financial support	Availability of financial support	Availability of consistent financial support
	x	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Complex and long bureaucracy requirements	Standard bureaucracy requirements	Easy-to-manage bureaucracy requirements
<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>	
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	Unfavourable policy context	Fair policy context	Encouraging policy context
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Lack of financial support	Availability of financial support	Availability of consistent financial support
	x	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Complex and long bureaucracy requirements	Standard bureaucracy requirements	Easy-to-manage bureaucracy requirements
<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>	
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	Unfavourable policy context	Fair policy context	Encouraging policy context
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	x
	Lack of financial support	Availability of financial support	Availability of consistent financial support
	<input type="checkbox"/>	x	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Complex and long bureaucracy requirements	Standard bureaucracy requirements	Easy-to-manage bureaucracy requirements
<input type="checkbox"/>	x*	<input type="checkbox"/>	

*Depends of the waste fraction.

Engagement of enterprises in promoting circular economy

In countries where enterprises and industries are traditionally engaged and interested in the creation of synergies and linkages, the realization of circular and innovative value chains can turn easier and more fruitful than under circumstances in which there is no interest for these strategies. In addition, a clear and concrete involvement of stakeholders in these mechanisms may encourage the development and implementation of actions of governments in the perspective of circular economy.

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Answer Summary

As LIPASAM is not responsible for commercial or industrial waste, it does not have sufficient verified information in this regard.

Engagement of enterprises in promoting circular economy			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low or none enterprises' effective commitment in circular economy implementation	Moderate enterprises' effective commitment in circular economy implementation	Notable enterprises' effective commitment in circular economy implementation
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"			
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"			
	X*	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

*We are on the way to be "moderate".

Customers' awareness about circular economy and environmental

Customers have been reported as strong drivers for greening activities and their demands have a strong influence on the decisions that companies take towards eco-design. The level of awareness about circular economy principles among customers is important because it leads to the shifting of user buying intention towards environmentally friendly goods, determining the success of a value chain, which depends directly on the end-users demand, generated by their perception and satisfaction. If citizens are properly educated about environmental themes, such as green labelling, marketing and advertising, it is more likely that they purchase, consume products designed according to environmentally sustainable principles, even in those cases when they are not particularly competitive on the market. Moreover, it is also more likely that they are careful in implementing the suggested actions for proper end-of-life management.

Answer Summary

In the city of Seville, the circular economy processes are not sufficiently studied, so we lack enough information. Specifically, we do not have information on the degree of participation or awareness of the different agents regarding biological, biodegradable or recyclable products.

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Engagement of enterprises in promoting circular economy			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low or none end-users' awareness about environmentally responsible purchases	Moderate end-users' awareness about environmentally responsible purchases	Notable end-users' awareness about environmentally responsible purchases
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"			
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"			
	X*	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

*This is more an intuition than a knowledge.

- **Considering the replicability self-assessment for all the requirements, overall, which demo case would you consider to be replicable in your local area?** (more than one answer can be provided)
 - DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"
 - DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"
 - X DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"
- **For the demo case(s) you considered as replicable, could you suggest one or more specific value chains (among those covered by the project, or similar) suitable to be implemented in the area of your city?**
Plastic, Organic waste or coked oil used.
- **Finally, which local actors would you identify to represent relevant roles in the possible implementation of such circular value chain(s)?**

DEMO CASE C, below.

Please amend the scheme proposed for the demo-cases you assessed (pick one only) as suitable for replicability by including local actors you would consider suitable to be integrated in a circular plastic packaging value chain

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DEMO CASE C “Enhanced sorting and recycling”

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6.7 ANNEX F – KARTAL INTERVIEW

Representative of Kartal Municipality

Technical Requirements

Availability and relevance of local resources

CIRC-PACK value chains are univocally based on key products and flows. An easy availability of materials and substances necessary for their manufacturing is crucial to facilitate and generate the installation of suitable plants, as well as waste flows needed for the generation of secondary raw materials to feed the value chains are produced in sufficient amount within the country.

The availability and relevance of local resources is thus determinant to guarantee continuous and reliable supply to stakeholders involved in the manufacturing phases, while contributing to minimize costs (economic, environmental) sustained for duties, logistic and transport. Also from of a social perspective, the involvement of local actors has positive effects, as it can contribute to improve the social acceptance of the innovative products, by creating local employment.

In Kartal, municipal solid waste is collected door-to-door mainly in 2 categories from all dwellings, offices, commercial places, schools, public institutions, markets etc.: packaging waste collected at the source and other solid wastes (not separated). The additional collection and separation from other solid waste is made by street collectors working illegally, these people enter in waste containers to take off the waste bags and sort the recyclable materials to sell to illegal waste collectors. This means some part of packaging waste is still collected but not registered.

Focusing on determining actual recyclable materials ratios in municipal solid waste, Kartal Municipality Environmental Protection and Control Directorate carried out waste characterisation analysis of municipal solid waste in 2015 in the framework of an academic master thesis, by collecting raw solid wastes from 3 different neighbourhoods and a commercial street selected by income level, then sorting them according to waste categories as kitchen wastes, paper, cardboard, plastic, glass, metal, electrical and electronic waste, hazardous waste (battery, medicine, paint box, etc.), park and garden waste, other non-combustible waste (stone, sand, ceramic, dust), other combustible bulky waste (cloth, diapers, shoes, slippers, pillows, etc.), other combustible bulky wastes (furniture, materials made of wood, etc.) and other non-combustible bulky wastes. The analysis results determined that kitchen wastes have the biggest share (57,69%) in the district and that packaging waste composed of paper, cardboard, glass, metal and plastics constitutes 26.53%, plastic wastes have a ratio of 8,41% in total municipal solid waste. The total daily municipal solid waste generated in total of 20 neighbourhoods was 463 tons in 2015 and 486 tons in 2016.

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Municipal Solid Waste Characterisation in Kartal by Economic Income Levels and Seasons (year 2015)											
Solid waste components	Seasonal Rate (%)								Seasonal Average Rate (%)		Yearly Average Rate (%)
	Low income (Hürriyet Neighbourhood)		Medium income (Petrol İş Neighbourhood)		High income (Orhantepe Neighbourhood)		Commercial (Soğanlık Yeni Neighbourhood)				
	Winter	Summer	Winter	Summer	Winter	Summer	Winter	Summer	Winter	Summer	Total
Kitchen waste	65,4	56,5	57,7	54,7	61,2	47,0	59,1	56,9	61,6	53,7	57,7
Paper	3,8	2,7	7,9	3,2	7,4	6,4	4,0	4,0	5,7	3,9	4,8
Cardboard	0,9	2,3	1,6	2,1	1,4	2,7	1,6	2,1	1,3	2,3	1,8
Bulky cardboard	2,5	5,2	3,7	8,2	3,6	4,0	3,0	4,5	3,1	5,6	4,4
Plastic	7,2	9,3	11,4	7,1	7,2	6,9	11,5	8,7	8,8	8,1	8,4
Glass	3,3	4,0	3,7	9,7	6,3	11,0	6,9	8,0	4,6	7,7	6,1
Metal	0,4	0,9	1,1	0,8	0,5	1,9	2,1	1,3	0,8	1,2	1,0
Bulky metal	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
Waste electric and electronic equipment	0,0	3,9	0,8	0,0	0,1	2,1	1,8	0,1	0,4	2,0	1,2
Hazardous waste	0,7	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,1	0,1	0,5	0,0	0,4	0,0	0,2
Park and garden wastes	0,6	2,9	0,1	2,5	4,0	11,2	0,0	1,0	1,3	4,6	2,9
Other incombustible waste	0,0	1,6	0,4	1,2	2,8	0,7	0,6	0,4	0,9	1,1	1,0
Other combustible waste	10,5	7,8	9,7	9,1	5,6	6,0	4,7	8,0	8,3	7,7	8,0
Other combustible bulky waste	0,01	2,9	2,1	1,3	0,0	0,0	4,4	4,9	1,1	2,1	1,6
Other incombustible bulky waste	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
Other	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
Ash (sand, soil, dust included)	4,6	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,7	0,0	0,9

According to this detailed waste characterisation, plastic waste composes 8,41% of the total municipal waste and 31,7% of the packaging waste.

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Summary Table for Packaging Waste (year 2015)						
Components	Ratio in Total Municipal Waste			Ratio in Packaging Waste		
	Winter	Summer	Yearly Average	Winter	Summer	Yearly Average
Paper	5,72	3,90	4,81	23,53	13,57	18,13
Cardboard	1,28	2,34	1,81	5,27	8,14	6,82
Bulky cardboard	3,14	5,58	4,36	12,92	19,41	16,43
Plastic	8,75	8,07	8,41	35,99	28,07	31,70
Glass	4,60	7,67	6,13	18,92	26,68	23,11
Metal	0,82	1,19	1,01	3,37	4,14	3,81
Total	24,31	28,75	26,53			

Comparing yearly collected waste data, the ratio of packaging waste collected separately from municipal solid waste in the source indicates increase while the amount and ratio of municipal solid waste sent to disposal decrease.

Waste type	Yearly collected waste							
	2016		2017		2018		2019	
	Amount (ton)	Ratio (%)	Amount (ton)	Ratio (%)	Amount (ton)	Ratio (%)	Amount (ton)	Ratio (%)
Municipal solid waste (1)	171.510	87,52	160.800	85,29	164.250	85,55	159.306	85,11
Rubble and slug (1)	17.993	9,18	20.300	10,77	18.783	9,78	18.428	9,85
Packaging waste (2)	7.445	3,80	7.529	3,99	8.971	4,67	9.443	5,04
TOTAL	195.958	100	188.529	100	192.004	100	187.177	100

- (1) collected by Cleaning Works Directorate to dispose in İstanbul Metropolitan Municipality sanitary landfill
- (2) collected separately at the source by Environmental Protection and Control Directorate to be sorted in licensed sorting plant

There is not enough actual data about the ratio of packaging waste in the municipal solid waste that is sent to disposal in sanitary landfill. The Cleaning Works Directorate assumed the solid waste components as a mean of 2015 and 2016 years values, giving the ratio of plastic packaging waste as 4 % and total packaging waste as 20%. In Kartal.

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Municipal Solid Waste Characterisation (sent to sanitary landfill) (mean of years 2015 and 2016)					
Solid waste components		kg/day	ton/month	ton/year	%
Organic		320.040	9.601,2	116.814,6	70
Packaging waste	Plastic	18.280	548,4	6.672,2	4
	Metal	9.140	274,2	3.336,1	2
	Glass	4.570	137,1	1.668,05	1
	Paper, Cardboard	54.860	1.645,8	20.023,9	12
	Composite	4.570	137,1	1.668,05	1
	Other	0	0	0	0
Ash, slug, soil etc.		45.720	1.371,6	16.687,8	10
TOTAL		457.180	13.906	166.870	

As the packaging waste sorted in licensed sorting plants is registered in the website of Ministry of Environment and Urbanisation, there is detailed data about the actual characterisation of packaging waste collected at the source and sorted in the plants. Composite waste is not collected. Plastic packaging waste ratio differs between 2,8 and 9,2%, in a decreasing pattern in Kartal.

Year	Collected Packaging Waste (Raw)	Paper-Cardboard		Glass		Plastic		Metal		Loss		Sorted Packaging Waste	
	ton	ton	%	ton	%	ton	%	ton	%	ton	%	ton	%
2009	1.433	1.347	94,0	0,6	0,04	68	4,8	3,8	0,3	-	-	1.419	99,1
2010	2.537	2.230	87,9	0,4	0,02	100	4,0	0,8	0,03	-	-	2.331	91,9
2011	2.863	2.142	74,8	117,5	4,1	238	8,3	51,2	1,8	-	-	2.548	89,0
2012	3.578	2.399	67,0	136	3,8	329	9,2	75,9	2,1	-	-	2.940	82,2
2013	3.830	1.9728	51,5	738	19,3	300	7,8	59,3	1,6	-	-	3.069	80,1
2014	5.062	3.334	65,9	1.157	22,9	261	5,2	27,6	0,6	282	5,6	4.780	94,4
2015	6.179	4.453	72,1	1.260	20,4	210	3,4	41,5	0,7	215	3,5	5.964	96,5
2016	7.445	5.416	72,8	1.383	18,6	459	6,2	9,3	0,1	178	2,4	6.052	81,3
2017	7.529	5.407	71,8	1.521	20,2	449	6,0	3,0	0,04	157	2,1	7.372	97,9
2018	8.971	6.850	76,4	1.575	17,6	372	4,2	4,8	0,05	170	1,9	8.802	98,1
2019	9.443	7.051	74,7	1.965	20,8	268	2,8	5,1	0,05	155	1,6	9.289	98,4
TOTAL	58.870	42.600	72,4	9.854	16,7	3.056	5,2	282,2	0,5	1.156	2,0	54.567	92,7

In Turkey, since 1 January 2020, the Zero Waste regulation orders to public institutions to establish waste collecting points in their buildings and collect wastes in separate bins according to waste categories, and then register the delivered amounts to the website of Ministry of Environment and Urbanisation with delivery documents. The private sector and residences also are going to be included according to schedule mentioned in the regulation. Since 2009, Kartal Municipality continues to collect packaging waste from residential, commercial, public buildings by periodic visits to buildings, delivers packaging

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waste collecting indoor bins and containers. The glass is collected both by glass containers on the streets and by packaging waste collection bins inside buildings. Information seminars are given to all schools and requesting residential places and workplaces to increase environmental awareness and encourage recyclable waste sorting habits, enhanced by campaigns.

The latest characterisation values of the plastic packaging waste collected and sorted in the licensed sorting plant mention that the ratio of plastic material decreases.

		Packaging Waste Collected at the source and Sorted			
		Year 2018		Year 2019	
Waste Category		Total (ton)	Rate (%)	Total (ton)	Rate (%)
Paper-Cardboard		6.850,40	76,36	7.050,69	74,66
Glass (sorted in plant)		5,53	0,06	3,92	0,04
Glass (sorted in source)		1.569,38	17,49	1.961,35	20,77
Plastic		372,00	4,15	267,98	2,84
	PE	167,90	1,87	111,70	1,18
	PET	57,35	0,64	44,05	0,47
	PVC	-	-	-	-
	PS	-	-	-	-
	PP	146,75	1,64	112,23	1,19
Tin		-	0,00	0,60	0,01
Aluminium		4,80	0,05	4,50	0,05
Composite		-	0,00	-	0,00
Collected Material		8.971,31	100,00	9.443,18	100,00
Loss		169,00	1,88	154,58	1,64
Sorted Material		8.801,71	98,11	9.288,59	98,36

Availability and relevance of local resources			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low availability of renewable feedstock	Fair availability of renewable feedstock	High availability of renewable feedstock
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-B	Low availability of local resources	Fair availability of local resources	High availability of local resources

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"Eco-friendly packaging design"	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	Low availability of local resources	Fair availability of local resources	High availability of local resources
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Waste collection and separation capacity

The capacity of collecting and sorting large amounts of waste is a driver for the implementation of successful and profitable value chains and symbioses. Such capacity derives from a combination of citizens' education to municipal waste management (or other wastes) and of the enforcement of efficient schemes for an adequate separate collection at municipal level. Proper collection and sorting have direct impact on waste reprocessing capacity and indirect impact on the availability of local resources.

How is the collection sorting for plastic and organic waste structured in Kartal? What are the quantities and which are the involved actors/companies? And what do they do (e.g. only collection; collection and sorting? Etc.)

In Kartal, there is not yet waste collecting center. The collecting is made at the source (residential, commercial, public building) by means of collecting materials delivered at building door periodically, once a week from dwellings and offices, 3 or 4 times a week from markets by a private licensed company who signed a contract with our municipality. It collects and sorts the material in its licensed sorting plant manually and compresses mechanically. The glass containers on the streets serve to public for sorting glass bottles and cans, emptied once or twice a month. Other municipal solid waste is collected by means of metal waste containers in front of each building on a daily basis.

Street collectors work for illegal packaging waste collectors taking the recyclable material from mixed waste containers in the streets and sometimes steal from packaging waste bins of the markets or dwellings. There are some illegal waste sorting places using abandoned industrial plots in Kartal. Despite the legal warnings and work offers, they do not accept to work for licensed plant.

Kartal Municipality is planning to establish and manage its packaging waste sorting plant in 2020.

Kartal has been an industrial city since 1950s due to its strategic position to transport lines and to the Marmara sea. The small and medium size enterprises are almost transferred their plants to other cities in Marmara region leaving their plots to residential use since the last 2 decades because of the rapid urban transformation trend in İstanbul. Therefore, there is a few enterprises continuing to process and reuse plastic raw and recycled material. Vatan Plastik and Cesur Packagingj are the main plastic packaging material manufacturers in Kartal. They have their own plastic sorting plant. Many packaging waste sorting plants also have left Kartal. There are still small size enterprises in automotive supply industry or repair. The primary sector is construction sector during the urban transformation.

Cesur Packaging is working in different cities and countries producing big bags, PP sacks, PE films. The firm states that production wastes such as PP, LDPE are recovered in the in-house recycling facility but are never used in their own production but are sold to

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masterbatch producers, injectioners and producers of low quality yarn for different usage areas, gaining economically with the process.

Vatan Plastic is producing greenhouse films, stretch film, shrink film, stretch hood, plasticisers, fluid plastics, additives and refuse sacks. The firm states that there are 2 recycling plants and Polyethylene (PE) and Polypropylene (PP) recycling operations are made in the facilities, that the obtained granules have certificate from Turkish Standards Institute, and that they purchase PE and PP Production / Package wastes from the companies.

In İstanbul, a few district municipalities have established their own packaging waste sorting plants.

In Turkey, the licensed sorting plant owners have problem to sell the collected material to manufacturers. The price and request of the manufacturers do not absorb the collecting, sorting and storage costs of the enterprises. They mention the main reason for decreasing price as the imported waste from EU and China during the last years.

Waste collection and separation capacity			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants for bio-based plastics	Fair availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants for bio-based plastics	High availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants for bio-based plastics
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	Low availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants	Fair availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants	High availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	Low availability of advanced separate collection schemes and sorting plants	Fair availability of advanced separate collection schemes and sorting plants	High availability of advanced separate collection schemes and sorting plants
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Waste reprocessing capacity

The technological capacity to reprocess multiple and large waste flows increases the potential of successful implementation of the value chains, allowing a greater availability of local resources (see previous requirement). Moreover, the presence of reprocessing plants is a proxy for the possibility of access – at local scale – to technologies and to technological background useful for the implementation of the desired value chains.

The reprocessing capacity is also valued at macro-scale level, waste reprocessing capacity is closely related to recovery and recycling rates for plastic and for packaging, which works as a transparent indicator for the availability of local resources, in terms of secondary raw materials and the possibility of recovering packaging waste at end-of-life.

How is the reprocessing/recycling for plastic and organic waste structured in Kartal? What are the quantities? Which are the involved companies?

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İSTAÇ (İstanbul Environment Management Industry and Trade Company), established by İstanbul Metropolitan Municipality in 1995, has 3 sanitary landfill sites to eliminate municipal wastes. 12.000 tons of unrecyclable waste is eliminated in European Site in Eyüp Göktürk Odayeri and Silivri Seymen Village, and 6.000 tons is eliminated in Asian Site in Şile Karakiraz Village Kömürcüoda by landfilling. The sanitary landfill sites where the leachate and gas management are made in a controlled manner, serve for 7/24. Garbage leachate having high contamination load is eliminated by not harming the nature, using membrane bioreactor + NF technology. The gas due to landfill is used in energy production by collecting through gas flues. The sanitary landfill in European side is designed to protect underground water.

	Sanitary Landfill Sites in İstanbul		
	Kömürcüoda	Odayeri	Seymen
Total licensed area (ha)	233 (65 is already used)	200 (126 is already used)	227
Daily waste load (ton/day)	5.500	10.500	500
Waste landfilled between 1994-2014 (million ton)	26	54	
Remaining landfill capacity (million ton)	40 (until year 2030)	62 (until year 2030)	74 (until year 2047)

Domestic solid wastes collected daily by district municipalities throughout İstanbul are transferred to larger vehicles at 8 solid waste transfer stations serving in various parts of the city and transported to disposal sites.

In solid waste storage sites, İSTAÇ produces electricity from landfill gas, reducing carbon emission, protecting the environment and contributing country economy. The landfill gases are burned under control in the production of energy in Odayeri and Kömürcüoda Landfill Sites, European and Asian sides respectively. Current electrical power production is 47 MW in Odayeri Landfill Site and 21 MW in Kömürcüoda Landfill Site. This energy produced from landfill solely, is sufficient for electricity needs of 1,2 millions population. Income received from production of electricity is used for city cleaning and to reduce the costs needed for other waste management activities.

İSTAÇ assumes the organic content of mixed municipal waste produced in İstanbul of 15,000 tons per day as 50%. The Recycling and Composting Facility serves to evaluate organic wastes in mixed municipal wastes, to recycle non-organic recyclable wastes and to reduce the amount of waste sent to landfills operating since 2001, established on 320,000 m² open area and 35,100 m² indoor area.

Organic wastes are evaluated in compost plants of İSTAÇ processing the wastes rich in organic content from vegetable markets and open bazaars as well as some part of collected wastes from towns to convert those into composts. Recycling and Composting Plant in Kemerburgaz is serving since 2001 as the biggest compost plant in Turkey, and one of the important composting plants worldwide, with a processing capacity of 1.000 tons per day of domestic wastes. It produces in average 20.000 tons per year of highly

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organic gardening compost. The compost has been examined in a TÜBİTAK (Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey) project approving its content rich in zinc. The compost is used in various park and gardens of Istanbul. After evaluation of waste characterisation of districts, wastes from regions having high organic component, high packaging waste rate and low textile waste rate are sent to this facility. Wastes from regional vegetable market, branch and knots from İstanbul Metropolitan cemeteries, parks and gardens and public and private sources also are delivered to this plant after sorting from mixed municipal solid waste, to be used after crumbling to increase the compost quality. The sorting unit in the Recycling and Composting Plant the recyclable PE, PP waste are granulated to produce granules and PET knot, average 4 ton of recyclable waste is recycled.

Industrial waste is evaluated and processed in solidification, stabilisation plants or sent to class 1 sanitary landfill, if waste is not available to process, it is sent to related disposal site from transfer station. İSTAÇ has reported its industrial waste processing capacity in 2018 as follows: Interim storage: 6.355-ton, Landfill: 136.214 ton, Handling: 2.175 ton, Solidification/Stabilisation: 2.901 ton.

İSTAÇ is collecting wastes from 515 km seashore all year and 4,5 million km² beaches area each summer. In 2018, packaging waste collected from seashore cleaning is 79 ton and from beaches is 65 ton.

The total cleaned area of 2 regional vegetable markets is 70.000m² per day.

İSTAÇ has planned the Kemberburgaz Biomethanisation Project to produce 11.200 MWh per year electric power using 130-ton biodegradable waste from organic solid waste such as food waste, vegetable waste, expired packaged food waste.

Waste reprocessing capacity			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low availability of treatment plants for bio-based plastics waste	Fair availability of treatment plants for bio-based plastics waste	High availability of treatment plants for bio-based plastics waste
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	Low availability of treatment plants for plastics waste	Fair availability of treatment plants for plastics waste	High availability of treatment plants for plastics waste
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	Low availability of advanced treatment plants for plastics waste	Fair availability of advanced treatment plants for plastics waste	High availability of advanced treatment plants for plastics waste
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Functional clusterization of industries on territory

The location and level of aggregation of industrial areas on the territory influences the way and the possibility of implementing industrial synergies. For example, if industries are highly clustered within a country i.e.: they are concentrated in industrial areas, easily accessible, exchanges between them can be implemented with limited effort. On the other hand, if industries are typically spread in different locations, which can also be isolated,

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interconnections may turn complex from a logistic and technical perspective, resulting in increased costs and environmental burdens.

Please describe the clusterization of relevant actors on the city territory (waste collectors, separators, incinerators, recyclers, manufacturers etc).

The clusterization of industries involved in the plastics value chain in Kartal is quite scattered. Only a few steps of the value chain are interconnected.

The main NGOs related to plastic industry in Turkey are PAGDER (Plastic Industrialists Association), PLASFED (Plastic Industrialists Federation), ASD (Packaging Waste Industrialists Association), PAGEV (Turkish Plastics Industry Foundation).

ÇEVKO (Environmental Protection and Packaging Waste Recovery and Recycling Trust), TÜKÇEV (Turkey Consumer and Environmental Education Foundation), AGED (Waste Paper and Recyclers Association) are the authorized bodies in managing, coordinating, supporting packaging waste collection, sorting, education, by the Ministry of Environment and Urbanisation mentioned in the Packaging Wastes Regulation.

HURSAN (Recycling and Environmental Technologies Industry Inc.) is the packaging waste collecting and sorting private company licensed to collect, transport and sort non-hazardous solid wastes by Ministry of Environment and Urbanisation, working for Kartal Municipality under contract and is member of TÛDAM (Recyclable Packaging Materials Collectors and Separators Association).

The main 2 plastic packaging products manufacturers are Cesur Packaging and Vatan Plastic in Kartal since decades.

Cesur Packaging is working in different cities and countries producing big bags, PP sacks, PE films. The firm states that production wastes such as PP, LDPE are recovered in the in-house recycling facility but are never used in their own production but are sold to masterbatch producers, injectioners and producers of low quality yarn for different usage areas, gaining economically with the process.

Vatan Plastic is producing greenhouse films, stretch film, shrink film, stretch hood, plasticisers, fluid plastics, additives and refuse sacks. The firm states that there are 2 recycling plants and Polyethylene (PE) and Polypropylene (PP) recycling operations are made in the facilities, that the obtained granules have certificate from Turkish Standards Institute, and that they purchase PE and PP Production / Package wastes from the companies.

In İstanbul, a few district municipalities have established their own packaging waste sorting plants.

Functional clusterization of industries on territory			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Segmented clusterization: (industries are not properly interconnected)	Fair clusterization	High clusterization: (industries are efficiently interconnected)
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"			

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Non-technical Requirements

A successful establishment of a value chain is triggered by the existence of a market demand for the end-products of the manufacturing process. Market demand is a crucial factor to positively activate and possibly sustain all the stages of each manufacturing chain. Within CIRCPACK project, a market analysis for the exploitation of the main results is performed. The analysis identifies categories of end users/customers potentially interested in the products obtained: as an example, manufacturers of primary, secondary, and tertiary plastic packaging may create demand for fully bio-degradable multilayer solutions and plastic packaging. The quantitative estimation of such demand can influence the decision of replicating a value chain in a certain country rather than in other.

How would you describe the market in Kartal (and in the closer region) for secondary materials? Are there manufacturers interested in buying recycled, multi-layer or bio-based materials? Are final customers interested in these products?

Cesur Packaging states that production wastes such as PP, LDPE are recovered in the in-house recycling facility but are never used in their own production but are sold to masterbatch producers, injectioners and producers of low quality yarn for different usage areas, gaining economically with the process.

Vatan Plastic states having 2 recycling plants for Polyethylene (PE) and Polypropylene (PP) recycling operations, that the obtained granules have certificate from Turkish Standards Institute, and that they purchase PE and PP Production / Packaging wastes from the companies.

The waste building materials, especially PVC windows and plastic pipe fittings, cables, and metal equipment such as baluster, window guards, heater core taken from demolished buildings during urban transformation are the main recycled materials the last years. These materials are always directly bought by second hand material sellers. The market is dynamic. The other main market is for paper and cardboard. As the raw material to produce paper and cardboard is much more expensive than before, the manufacturers prefer to use recycled paper and cardboard. The material is imported or recycled.

Composite packaging is not favourable to collect because of high recycling cost, so the collecting is not made with packaging waste.

Biobased material is used in promotional products such as sprouting pencil, blocknote, greeting card with seed ball etc.

Existence of a market demand			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low end-users demand of bio-based products	Fair end-users demand of bio-based products	High end-users demand of bio-based products
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	Low end-users demand of recoverable products	Fair end-users demand of recoverable products	High end-users demand of recoverable products
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	Low manufacturers demand of secondary raw materials	Fair manufacturers demand of secondary raw materials	High manufacturers demand of secondary raw materials
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

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Support of governments to improve circular value chains: policy framework, financing and administrative burden

Opportunities and drivers promoted by governments may act as determinant facilitators for the implementation of circular economy strategies.

In recent years, several policy actions at EU level have been focusing on circular economy and associated business models. On 2 December 2015, the European Commission put forward a package to support the EU's transition to a circular economy. The EU Action Plan for the Circular Economy outlines a set of both general and material-specific actions.

The circular economy has also gained momentum in the policies of Members States, largely due to the political priority given to it by the EU in recent years. Some MS have developed dedicated circular economy strategies and roadmaps (France, Netherlands, Finland, etc.). A growing number of regions (Flanders, the Basque country, etc.) are now acting to develop a circular economy and they have been joined by a number of cities (Amsterdam, London, etc.). Some have adopted circular economy strategies, while others have introduced the circular economy in their sectoral policies (waste, economy, agriculture, bio-economy, construction etc.).

The main enablers that can be offered with the aim of supporting the creation and development of circular value chain within a country include:

- the **enforcement of a consistent national policy framework**, effectively addressing responsibilities across all the stages of the value chains, involving all the interested stakeholders, from the manufacturing phase to waste collection and management and to reprocessing activities;
- the **financial and economic aspects of a project** are naturally crucial elements for replication. A sound project's financing analysis should be based on the evaluation, inter alia, of the following elements: financial costs, financial risks, hidden and unforeseen costs, and financial solutions. The allocation of national funds can facilitate and unlock the implementation of value chains presenting economic criticalities. They can be offered in form of incentives, tax reductions, grant, etc. A positive financial influence from governments contribute to increase innovative products' price competitiveness against traditional products on the market;
- **minimization of bureaucracy requirements** to get access to the available instruments, including an adequate presence of offices, hiring of sufficient appointed staff, online platform for remote access to services.

How would you describe the regional and national framework relevant for Kartal and in Turkey in general with regard to building local circular value chains?

Packaging Waste Regulation and Zero Waste Regulation control the production, collection, sorting and recycling of packaging materials, forcing municipalities to organize the regular collection and reporting of the waste management steps with the support of licensed firms and authorized bodies, responding to the material and information requests of local people, to ensure collection of regulated target rates. The municipalities have the right to realize the waste collection by their own facility or to

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assign a licensed company by contract. The cost of collecting materials is afforded by the licensed firms and authorized bodies. The government does not support the financial needs in establishment of waste collecting centers or waste sorting plants. In Turkey, the licensed sorting plant owners have problem selling the collected material to manufacturers. The price and request of the manufacturers do not absorb the collecting, sorting and storage costs of the enterprises. They mention the main reason for decreasing price as the imported waste from EU and China during the last years. The local circular value chain is difficult to establish while the imported material is in the market.

Support of governments to improve circular value chains			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Unfavourable policy context	Fair policy context	Encouraging policy context
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Lack of financial support	Availability of financial support	Availability of consistent financial support
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	Complex and long bureaucracy requirements	Standard bureaucracy requirements	Easy-to-manage bureaucracy requirements
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Unfavourable policy context	Fair policy context	Encouraging policy context
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	Lack of financial support	Availability of financial support	Availability of consistent financial support
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Complex and long bureaucracy requirements	Standard bureaucracy requirements	Easy-to-manage bureaucracy requirements
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Engagement of enterprises in promoting circular economy

In countries where enterprises and industries are traditionally engaged and interested in the creation of synergies and linkages, the realization of circular and innovative value chains can turn easier and more fruitful than under circumstances in which there is no interest for

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these strategies. In addition, a clear and concrete involvement of stakeholders in these mechanisms may encourage the development and implementation of actions of governments in the perspective of circular economy.

How do companies engage in Kartal to promote circular economy?

Engagement of enterprises in promoting circular economy			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low or none enterprises' effective commitment in circular economy implementation	Moderate enterprises' effective commitment in circular economy implementation	Notable enterprises' effective commitment in circular economy implementation
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"			
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"			
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Customers' awareness about circular economy and environmental

Customers have been reported as strong drivers for greening activities and their demands have a strong influence on the decisions that companies take towards eco-design. The level of awareness about circular economy principles among customers is important because it leads to the shifting of user buying intention towards environmentally friendly goods, determining the success of a value chain, which depends directly on the end-users demand, generated by their perception and satisfaction. If citizens are properly educated about environmental themes, such as green labelling, marketing and advertising, it is more likely that they purchase, consume products designed according to environmentally sustainable principles, even in those cases when they are not particularly competitive on the market. Moreover, it is also more likely that they are careful in implementing the suggested actions for proper end-of-life management.

How aware are final customers on the circular economy, in particular with regard to bio-based, biodegradable or recyclable products?

According to public survey carried out online by 269 Kartal residents and 790 Turkish people in the framework of T7.6 in CIRC-PACK project; Turkish respondents are highly willing to buy low-environmental impact products and they also are ambitious to do it even if it implies a higher price.

The rate of collecting packaging waste increases day by day. The plastic waste contamination in drinking water PET bottles, in the oceans and seas is highlighted by environmental NGOs on media and people is getting more attentive in buying recyclable packaging and sorting plastic wastes in collecting bins. The customer interest in biodegradable detergents in markets is increasing.

Since the start of having to pay for market bag due to the Zero Waste regulation, people uses their textile bags or reuses old market bag, causing 80% decrease in using new plastic bag bought in market.

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Engagement of enterprises in promoting circular economy			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low or none end-users' awareness about environmentally responsible purchases	Moderate end-users' awareness about environmentally responsible purchases	Notable end-users' awareness about environmentally responsible purchases
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"			
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"			
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

- **Considering the replicability self-assessment for all the requirements, overall, which demo case would you consider to be replicable in your local area?** (more than one answer can be provided)

- DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"
- DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"
- DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"

- **For the demo case(s) you considered as replicable, could you suggest one or more specific value chains (among those covered by the project, or similar) suitable to be implemented in the area of your city?**

.....

- **Finally, which local actors would you identify to represent relevant roles in the possible implementation of such circular value chain(s)?**

Vatan Plastic and Cesur Packaging companies should be interested in new technologies for eco-friendly design and reuse recycled material.

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DEMO CASE A “Plastics from renewable resources”

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6.8 ANNEX H – PORTO INTERVIEW

Representative of Porto Ambiente municipal waste management company

Technical Requirements

Availability and relevance of local resources

CIRC-PACK value chains are univocally based on key products and flows. An easy availability of materials and substances necessary for their manufacturing is crucial to facilitate and generate the installation of suitable plants, as well as waste flows needed for the generation of secondary raw materials to feed the value chains are produced in sufficient amount within the country.

The availability and relevance of local resources is thus determinant to guarantee continuous and reliable supply to stakeholders involved in the manufacturing phases, while contributing to minimize costs (economic, environmental) sustained for duties, logistic and transport. Also from of a social perspective, the involvement of local actors has positive effects, as it can contribute to improve the social acceptance of the innovative products, by creating local employment.

Overall, what are the fractions you deal with in Porto? What quantities do you collect for each fraction? (Focus specifically on plastic packaging and organic waste. A small table or graph could also be used)

Municipal waste	144 830 t		
Mixed waste		115 390 t	
Selective collection		40 980 t	
Glass			6 030 t
Plastic & Metal packaging			3 380 t
Paper & Cardboard			6 200 t
Green waste			4 600 t
Food waste			6 940 t
Other selective			13 830 t

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Availability and relevance of local resources			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low availability of renewable feedstock	Fair availability of renewable feedstock	High availability of renewable feedstock
		X	
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	Low availability of local resources	Fair availability of local resources	High availability of local resources
		X	
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	Low availability of local resources	Fair availability of local resources	High availability of local resources
		X	

Waste collection and separation capacity

The capacity of collecting and sorting large amounts of waste is a driver for the implementation of successful and profitable value chains and symbioses. Such capacity derives from a combination of citizens' education to municipal waste management (or other wastes) and of the enforcement of efficient schemes for an adequate separate collection at municipal level. Proper collection and sorting have direct impact on waste reprocessing capacity and indirect impact on the availability of local resources.

How is the collection sorting for plastic and organic waste structured in Porto? What are the quantities, and which are the involved actors/companies? And what do they do (e.g. only collection; collection and sorting? Etc.)

By the Portuguese Law, the Municipalities are the entities responsible for the municipal waste management. Since 2017, the Municipal Environmental Company of Porto (EMAP - Porto Ambiente) is the entity responsible for the waste management system and the urban cleaning services, that include deposit, collection and transport of the waste produced in the city of Porto.

The waste collection system is only public, so we don't have private company operate.

Selective collection system of plastic packaging and of food waste:

- Door-to-Door in households (pilot project with 2000 participants), using small containers;

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- Door-to-Door in commerce (with 800 participants), using plastic bags for packaging and a bin for food waste;
- Street bins (1150 containers), only for packaging. However, by the end of this year (2020), Porto will implement a project for food waste collection using street bins. Initially, this project will serve 30% of Porto's population and will be implemented on a residential pilot area with high rise buildings.

The city of Porto and other 7 cities of the metropolitan area created LIPOR - Intermunicipal Waste Management System, which is a Municipality Association, for the treatment of the urban waste produced in these municipalities. LIPOR has a sorting plant for packaging and a composting plant for treatment of biowaste.

Waste collection and separation capacity			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants for bio-based plastics	Fair availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants for bio-based plastics	High availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants for bio-based plastics
	X		
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	Low availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants	Fair availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants	High availability of separate collection schemes and sorting plants
		X	
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	Low availability of advanced separate collection schemes and sorting plants	Fair availability of advanced separate collection schemes and sorting plants	High availability of advanced separate collection schemes and sorting plants
			X

Waste reprocessing capacity

The technological capacity to reprocess multiple and large waste flows increases the potential of successful implementation of the value chains, allowing a greater availability of local resources (see previous requirement). Moreover, the presence of reprocessing plants is a proxy for the possibility of access –at local scale – to technologies and to technological background useful for the implementation of the desired value chains.

The reprocessing capacity is also valued at macro-scale level, waste reprocessing capacity is closely related to recovery and recycling rates for plastic and for packaging, which works as a transparent indicator for the availability of local resources, in terms of secondary raw materials and the possibility of recovering packaging waste at end-of-life.

How is the reprocessing/recycling for plastic and organic waste structured in Porto? What are the quantities? Which are the involved companies?

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In LIPOR, based on the fraction of waste received, the materials are forwarded to different plants. In terms of plastic waste, LIPOR has a sorting plant where the materials are sorted into plastic film, PET, HDPE, PVC, tetra-pack, aluminium, metal, mixed plastics, paper and cardboard. The sorted waste is then forwarded to recycling companies throughout Portugal. When it comes to organic waste, LIPOR has an organic valorisation plant, where the organic material is composed into a natural, high quality organic compost – Nutrimais – sold directly by LIPOR to final consumers. This compost is also used by LIPOR as a teaching tool, in their workshops about organic farming.

The quantities received and treated in LIPOR are shown in the table below. It's important to mention that the rate of rejected is about 8%, which indicates the quality of the selective waste collected.

Quantities from LIPOR (2019)

Total waste	550 080 t		
Mixed waste		402 705 t	
Multi-material		70 577 t	
Plastic and Metal Packaging			12 386 t
Biowaste		58 791 t	
Food Waste			32 888 t
Green Waste			25 903 t

Waste reprocessing capacity			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low availability of treatment plants for bio-based plastics waste	Fair availability of treatment plants for bio-based plastics waste	High availability of treatment plants for bio-based plastics waste
	X		
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	Low availability of treatment plants for plastics waste	Fair availability of treatment plants for plastics waste	High availability of treatment plants for plastics waste
		X	
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	Low availability of advanced treatment plants for plastics waste	Fair availability of advanced treatment plants for plastics waste	High availability of advanced treatment plants for plastics waste
	X		

Functional clusterization of industries on territory

The location and level of aggregation of industrial areas on the territory influences the way and the possibility of implementing industrial synergies. For example, if industries are highly clustered within a country i.e.: they are concentrated in industrial areas, easily accessible, exchanges between them can be implemented with limited effort. On the other hand, if industries are typically spread in different locations, which can also be isolated,

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interconnections may turn complex from a logistic and technical perspective, resulting in increased costs and environmental burdens.

Please describe the clusterization of relevant actors on the city territory (waste collectors, separators, incinerators, recyclers, manufacturers etc).

As already mentioned, Porto Ambiente is the entity responsible for the collection and transportation of waste. The collected waste then follows to LIPOR. Since LIPOR is the entity responsible to make the connection between the waste collectors (in this case, Porto Ambiente), and the recyclers, it allows for a clusterization of the relevant actors, with LIPOR having the main role and being the center of this cluster. However, this clusterization doesn't take place in the city of Porto and is not a geographical clusterization.

In Porto's city territory, we can only identify clusters of manufacturers, corresponding to small industrial areas. In terms of waste collectors, separators or recyclers, there isn't a clear territorial cluster that can be identified, since much of these actors are established in the peripheral cities.

Functional clusterization of industries on territory			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Segmented clusterization: (industries are not properly interconnected)	Fair clusterization	High clusterization: (industries are efficiently interconnected)
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"			
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	X		

Non-technical requirements

Existence of a market demand

A successful establishment of a value chain is triggered by the existence of a market demand for the end-products of the manufacturing process. Market demand is a crucial factor to positively activate and possibly sustain all the stages of each manufacturing chain. Within CIRCPACK project, a market analysis for the exploitation of the main results is performed. The analysis identifies categories of end users/customers potentially interested in the products obtained: as an example, manufacturers of primary, secondary, and tertiary plastic packaging may create demand for fully bio-degradable multilayer solutions and plastic packaging. The quantitative estimation of such demand can influence the decision of replicating a value chain in a certain country rather than in other.

How would you describe the market in Porto (and in the closer region) for secondary materials? Are there manufacturers interested in buying recycled, multi-layer or bio-based materials? Are final customers interested in these products?

In Porto, as in Portugal, more and more there is a search for secondary materials, with larger companies, with a big impact in the Portuguese market, having the concern of using mainly

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recycled materials. Nowadays, it's common to find products either from 100% recycled materials or with a 50%+ recycled materials base. In terms of bio-based materials, considering its broader meaning, they always have been a reality in Porto's and Portuguese culture, with, for example, the use of cork as one of our major raw materials. However, considering bio-based materials as materials manufactured from a biological derivative, the search is now beginning, with smaller companies and universities playing a major role in the development and diffusion of these kind of products.

The changes we are beginning to see in the market, with easily available products made from recycled, multi-layer or bio-based materials, reflect the existing demand. The final customers do have an interest in buying these kinds of products, as the environmental awareness grows. However, the cost of these products, usually bigger than non-recycled products, is a downside that affects the choice in the moment of purchase.

Existence of a market demand			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low end-users demand of bio-based products	Fair end-users demand of bio-based products	High end-users demand of bio-based products
		X	
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	Low end-users demand of recoverable products	Fair end-users demand of recoverable products	High end-users demand of recoverable products
		X	
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	Low manufacturers demand of secondary raw materials	Fair manufacturers demand of secondary raw materials	High manufacturers demand of secondary raw materials
		X	

Support of governments to improve circular value chains: policy framework, financing and administrative burden

Opportunities and drivers promoted by governments may act as determinant facilitators for the implementation of circular economy strategies.

In recent years, several policy actions at EU level have been focusing on circular economy and associated business models. On 2 December 2015, the European Commission put forward a package to support the EU's transition to a circular economy. The EU Action Plan for the Circular Economy outlines a set of both general and material-specific actions.

The circular economy has also gained momentum in the policies of Members States, largely due to the political priority given to it by the EU in recent years. Some MS have developed dedicated circular economy strategies and roadmaps (France, Netherlands, Finland, etc.). A growing number of regions (Flanders, the Basque country, etc.) are now acting to develop a circular economy and they have been joined by a number of cities (Amsterdam, London, etc.). Some have adopted circular economy strategies, while others have introduced the

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circular economy in their sectoral policies (waste, economy, agriculture, bio-economy, construction etc.).

The main enablers that can be offered with the aim of supporting the creation and development of circular value chain within a country include:

- the **enforcement of a consistent national policy framework**, effectively addressing responsibilities across all the stages of the value chains, involving all the interested stakeholders, from the manufacturing phase to waste collection and management and to reprocessing activities;
- the **financial and economic aspects of a project** are naturally crucial elements for replication. A sound project's financing analysis should be based on the evaluation, inter alia, of the following elements: financial costs, financial risks, hidden and unforeseen costs, and financial solutions. The allocation of national funds can facilitate and unlock the implementation of value chains presenting economic criticalities. They can be offered in form of incentives, tax reductions, grant, etc. A positive financial influence from governments contribute to increase innovative products' price competitiveness against traditional products on the market;
- **minimization of bureaucracy requirements** to get access to the available instruments, including an adequate presence of offices, hiring of sufficient appointed staff, online platform for remote access to services.

How would you describe the regional and national framework relevant for Porto and in Portugal in general with regard to building local circular value chains?

Portugal has made commitments for which the measures of the Circular Economy Action Plan compete, such as the Paris Agreement and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals 2030. It is also aligned with European policies, including the EU Circular Economy Action Plan and the EU Industrial Policy Strategy.

The Government has defined several initiatives such as a Strategy to Combat Food Waste, methodologies for classification of by-products, reduce the single use plastic, extraction and regeneration of materials with added value from waste streams. The implementation of these actions will be supported through some financial instruments like Fund for Innovation, Technology and Circular Economy, Environmental Fund and EU funds (Programme Portugal 2020).

In Porto, the Circular Economy is a key theme in the Municipal Environment Strategy in which we have been putting not only our attention, but a substantial part of our effort with very concrete actions. An example of this effort is the completion of the first version of the "Roadmap" for Porto's Circular Economy at the end of 2017.

This "Roadmap" aims to identify opportunities and guidelines, build a long-term vision and subsequently support a program of concrete actions of the Municipality - in order to transform the Port into a circular city in 2030.

The transformation of a circular city is a complex process that depends on the involvement of multiple actors such as companies, universities, technology and research centers, citizens or non-governmental organizations. The role of the Municipality is to create the necessary

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conditions for the full involvement of all relevant actors, and can do so, from the outset, through the "example" in how it will guide the acquisition of goods and services with circularity concerns. It can and should also seek to catalyze and facilitate the capacity and willingness of companies to transform environmental and social challenges into business opportunities, or by raising awareness among citizens to make more informed choices.

Support of governments to improve circular value chains			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Unfavourable policy context	Fair policy context	Encouraging policy context
			x
	Lack of financial support	Availability of financial support	Availability of consistent financial support
		x	
	Complex and long bureaucracy requirements	Standard bureaucracy requirements	Easy-to-manage bureaucracy requirements
		x	
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"	Unfavourable policy context	Fair policy context	Encouraging policy context
			x
	Lack of financial support	Availability of financial support	Availability of consistent financial support
			x
	Complex and long bureaucracy requirements	Standard bureaucracy requirements	Easy-to-manage bureaucracy requirements
		x	
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"	Unfavourable policy context	Fair policy context	Encouraging policy context
			x
	Lack of financial support	Availability of financial support	Availability of consistent financial support
			x
	Complex and long bureaucracy requirements	Standard bureaucracy requirements	Easy-to-manage bureaucracy requirements
		x	

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Engagement of enterprises in promoting circular economy

In countries where enterprises and industries are traditionally engaged and interested in the creation of synergies and linkages, the realization of circular and innovative value chains can turn easier and more fruitful than under circumstances in which there is no interest for these strategies. In addition, a clear and concrete involvement of stakeholders in these mechanisms may encourage the development and implementation of actions of governments in the perspective of circular economy.

How do companies engage in Porto to promote circular economy?

LIPOR, together with European Recycling Platform (ERP), has developed a new strategy in order to give a second life to equipment that would previously be thrown away, involving the community and empowering it in this new solution for Waste Electrical and Electronic.

Thus, is born the CREW network - Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment Recovery Centers, which function as training and capacity spaces, which promote the recovery of Waste electrical and electronic equipment.

In addition, there are other projects dedicated to combating food waste, such as "DOSE CERTA", "EMBRULHA", FAIRMEALS, etc.

Other examples:

- **Libraries:** School book exchange programme (e.g. "TROQUE");
- **Markets for the sale of used materials, urban crafts and reuse:** Flea Market Porto (and use of abandoned silo); Pink Market; Porto Belo Market; Urban Market; Market Place;
- **Green purchasing:** Sustainable public procurement system; Product lifecycle concerns integrated into city council tenders or acquisitions criteria (within the existing legal framework);
- **Cidade+:** Event of dissemination of knowledge of good practices in sustainability that aggregates different stakeholders;
- **Pedagogical Gardens:** Community spaces that educate the population in contact with natural cycles.

Engagement of enterprises in promoting circular economy			
DC-A "Plastics from renewable resources"	Low or none enterprises' effective commitment in circular economy implementation	Moderate enterprises' effective commitment in circular economy implementation	Notable enterprises' effective commitment in circular economy implementation
DC-B "Eco-friendly packaging design"			
DC-C "Enhanced sorting and recycling"		x	

Customers' awareness about circular economy and environmental

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Customers have been reported as strong drivers for greening activities and their demands have a strong influence on the decisions that companies take towards eco-design. The level of awareness about circular economy principles among customers is important because it leads to the shifting of user buying intention towards environmentally friendly goods, determining the success of a value chain, which depends directly on the end-users demand, generated by their perception and satisfaction. If citizens are properly educated about environmental themes, such as green labelling, marketing and advertising, it is more likely that they purchase, consume products designed according to environmentally sustainable principles, even in those cases when they are not particularly competitive on the market. Moreover, it is also more likely that they are careful in implementing the suggested actions for proper end-of-life management.

How aware are final customers on the circular economy, in particular with regard to bio-based, biodegradable or recyclable products?

The term “circular economy” is still not known to most of the final costumers. Nonetheless, there is, as mentioned before, a growing environmental concern that will reflect positively in the circular economy. The most current theme is the abolition of single use plastics, which leads to a search of alternative products, mainly those who are bio-based or recyclable/recycled.

As also mentioned before, not only does the “environmental factor” weighs in when the time comes to decide between two products – the most important factor, to most final customers, continues to be the price. This leads to a devaluation of the environmental responsible aspect of purchasing, since the cost does not justify the origin of the product. However, on the plus side, the recycling rates have been growing in Porto as never before, which shows that, although the products may not have a bio-based, biodegradable or recycled origin, they will be injected in the circular economy. So, it's essential to invest continuously in citizens, giving them the necessary information and raising their awareness, because they are final customers and make the final decisions, and therefore the economy will not be circular.

Engagement of enterprises in promoting circular economy			
DC-A “Plastics from renewable resources”	Low or none end-users' awareness about environmentally responsible purchases	Moderate end-users' awareness about environmentally responsible purchases	Notable end-users' awareness about environmentally responsible purchases
DC-B “Eco-friendly packaging design”			
DC-C “Enhanced sorting and recycling”		X	